

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable we present the Virtual User Models of the workers (wVUMs) and the Workplace Models of the Ageing@Work platform. The aim of the wVUM is to persist and represent information about the skills, needs, requirements, behaviour activities and health issues of the worker both at workplace and at home. To this end, the wVUM is a representation of physiological, psychometrics, anthropometrics, behavioural, workability and socialization parameters describing each worker both at work and at home, with the aim to provide personalized tools to ageing workers according to their actual needs and status and improve both their quality of life and productivity. Furthermore, the computational part of the wVUM is able to utilise rules and predictions according to worker's behavior, in order to deliver individualized recommendations and reinforce worker's improved well-being. In this context for example, physical inactivity can be predicted through the application of machine learning techniques, thereby providing the means (e.g., through virtual coaching) to warn the workers about unhealthy behaviours in advance and promote their improved health and lifestyle management. The wVUMs are able to communicate their persisted information to the Ageing@Work apps through well-defined application programming interfaces (APIs) based on the Representational State Transfer (REST) architecture, towards the provision of a robust and extensible solution.

In addition, in this deliverable we present the Ageing@Work framework for developing Virtual Workplace Models (VWM), coupled with user-friendly possibilities to add semantic annotations on the machines and tools used, and capabilities to model work tasks and scenarios. The opportunity to simulate work tasks in virtual environments allows to avoid onsite learning on real machines and facilitates the practice of potentially dangerous actions while providing the possibility for unlimited remote training experience. A VWM schema is first introduced that supports environmental factors along with modelling parameters of a working space (in industrial, office or home settings) in several layers of representation (3D point clouds, meshes, etc) along with the necessary kinematic and interaction properties.

The use of those tools for the realistic representation of a virtual workplace, mirroring the actual work environment can help the design and preview of work spaces, adjusted on ergonomics, efficiency and other measurable factors. Therefore, the work in this deliverable on VWMs provides the necessary tools and models to support other tasks in of Ageing@Work activities (mainly T3.4, T3.5 and T6.2), as they will allow to assess the individual worker's ergonomics and work process specificities as well as overall work orchestration, enabling inference on optimized, age-friendly work arrangements.

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List of Terms and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
wVUM	Worker Virtual User Model
DHM	Digital Human Model
VWM	Virtual Workplace Model
UML	Unified Modeling Language
QoL	Quality of Life
REST	Representational State Transfer
AR	Augmented Reality
MET	Metabolic Equivalent of Task
HT	Hold Time
FT	Flight Time
JSON	Javascript Object Notation
COPSOQ	Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire for Job Satisfaction
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology
API	Application Programming Interface
MEM	Maximum Entropy Method
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
SOAP	Simple Object Access Protocol
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
TOF	Time of Flight
RBF	Radial Basis Functions
RELU	Rectified Linear Unit
CPU	Central Processing Unit
HD	Hausdorff Distance
CAD	Computer-aided Design
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HD	Hausdorff Distance
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

Table 1 Definitions

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the Deliverable

The objectives described in this deliverable is to present the development of Ageing@Work worker Virtual User Model and Virtual Workplace models for machine readable representations. The first virtual model encodes the worker's profile by including physical, cognitive and behavioural information both at work and leisure time and the latter one encodes physical and process aspects which are assigned based on optimization rules to the workers. The assignment is based on computational intelligence which provides simulations-based predictive assessment.

The wVUM is built upon the results of the analysis on ageing worker skills, productivity and human factors which are described in D3.1 Human factors and metrics analysis. The wVUMs of the Ageing@Work system has been an extension of VERITAS outcomes in order to fit into the specificities regarding well-being status of ageing workers. The model represents a digital worker, which is designed by taking into consideration factors from both workplace behaviours, requirements, and personal life activities (out of the workplace environment). The questionnaire to be used for initializing a wVUM is a combination of validated questions that include demographics, PHQ-9 items, Big Five – S items, SF12 items and COPSOQ items. After initializing all worker models, the project's solution is evaluated with the SF12, COPSOQ and UTAUT questionnaires from which the data are kept in wVUM for further analysis. The aim is to create two indexes measuring productivity at work and reassurance of leisure time which result in an improvement of the main index of Quality of Life.

The model considers multiple dimensions of a worker's life which affect the execution of a specific task in a context defined by the VWUMs in T3.3 Virtual Workplace Models. The initialization of these dimensions is presented which is achieved with a measurement campaign in the beginning of the pilots and then updated every 6 months. Moreover, enrichment of wVUMs parameters is achieved by using apps that monitor the worker behaviour both at work and at home, enabling wVUMs to remain tailored to the user as time progresses. The computational part of the wVUM is also presented in the deliverable, showing the rule-based logic for the A@W system data collection and cognition, along with predictive assessment capabilities. In this regard, our work for sedentary behaviour prediction is presented to highlight the forecasting potential of the wVUM.

Regarding the Virtual Workplace modelling, in this deliverable, we will present the developed tools and techniques for (i) the utilization of 3D scanning technologies and development of 3D (point cloud and mesh) processing methods and algorithms to reduce noise and outliers, as well as the effect of missing parts (due to imperfect scanning), (ii) the development of authoring tools for the creation of models based on shape primitives (as "digital twins" of the actual objects and machines), (iii) the introduction of a semantic and interaction layer on the developed models, and (iv) the introduction of capabilities for simulation of work tasks and scenarios as a sequence of pre-defined actions. The notion a digital human model (DHM) acting in the simulated environment allows to connect with the 1st part of the deliverable (on the wVUM) and personalize the simulations.

1.2 Relation to Other Activities and Deliverables

The deliverable is part of Task 3.2 – The Ageing@Work Virtual Worker Models and Task 3.3 – The Ageing@Work Virtual Workplace Models. The deliverable takes into account initial profiling parts for the Virtual Worker and Workplace Models established in D3.1, therefore it involves collection and analysis of the end-users requirements in order to establish users' categories and preferences. Moreover, it exploits results acquired by surveys, interviews and focus groups sessions for extensive user modelling work that was done in terms of WP2 User requirements, system specification and architecture.

The part of the deliverable on the VWM describing the semantic layer for simulation-based assessment of a working task and ergonomics optimization is closely related with deliverable D3.3 (to be submitted in the next period). Moreover, the developed model structures and definitions are used for the development of VR and AR based learning tutorials and training tutorial, thus there is a relation with the task D6.2.

1.3 Structure of the Deliverable

In Section 2 we provide a detailed description of the wVUM and its dimensions to represent workers. We specifically show the baseline demographic, physiological, psychological and social parameters persisted in wVUM along with workability, productivity, lifestyle and behavioural monitoring information. Furthermore, we show the way that the wVUM is initialized, continuously updated through the use of Ageing@Work tools and used for impact assessment purposes. In Section 3, we present the computational part of the wVUM, focusing on the rule-based logic for storing worker's information, as well as its capabilities to predict worker behaviour, with emphasis on the prediction of physical inactivity. In Section 4 the wVUM communication capabilities through REST APIs are presented. After presentation of the wVUM, we present our virtual workplace modelling approach starting with the demonstration of the VWM schematic (Section 5). Then the Geometry Layer is described which includes the 3D modeling and 3D scanning techniques followed by illustration of some results. Next, we describe the developed Geometry Processing Tools including an automatic floor extraction methodology and various novel 3D mesh denoising techniques implemented by UPAT. The deliverable continues with the presentation of the Semantic Layer of VWM necessary for the flexible modelling of workspace tasks and scenarios. Finally, we present some application examples, as well as high level UML semantic overview of the workplace and scheduling entities and relationships. Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

2. VUM Representation

2.1 High Level View

The Ageing@Work advanced virtual workers' model is developed in a way that enables the study of various information and describes them in an effort to find key goal parameters that affect an age-friendly and fit-for-purpose working and living environment. The aim of the worker's virtual user model (wVUM) is to keep classified information about the skills, needs, requirements, behaviour activities and health issues both at workplace and private life, either inside or outside home. Moreover, the VUMs are used in order to offer three core processes of the project in a highly personalized way. The first one is a personalization of ICT tools like the productivity enhancement tool and the virtual assistant, second process is a personalized predictive assessment of the worker's trends through.

Quality of Life and Workability needs and lastly, personalized suggestions on work ergonomics, scheduling, health and well-being factors. The models are dynamic and extensible and are updated with new observations jointly related to workability and well-being of ageing, allowing the actual representation of real workers' conditions.

Therefore, VUM is a representation of physical, sensorial, socialization and cognitive parameters describing each worker both at work and at home. This multi-factor model is accompanied with information about interests of the worker, skills and behaviour at work as well as at leisure time. This information formulates two basic indexes for measuring the Quality of Life of the worker, one is the Workability and the second is his/her well-being.

Thus, for each user, the VUM keeps demographic information, which is necessary for defining heterogeneity of user groups, like older employees for whom tailored operating systems are addressed. In terms of anthropometrics, there is information kept for digital human modelling in order to appropriately adapt the computer-aided design (CAD) platforms which have built-in ergonomic capabilities.

A distinct information section kept in VUM regards fundamental activity and behaviour data which are separated into physical, cognitive, mood and social activities. For physical health, chronic impairments, and diseases along with HR measurements give a view of the worker's status daily. Cognitive and mood assessment is offering knowledge that enhances more personalized recommendations offered by the project's solution. Social activities along with job factors support the evaluation of QoL since they inform about personal life habits and workability. These data help in continuous monitoring of the workers in order to minimize work-related risks and optimize the workplace ergonomics and assignment of tasks. Moreover, it helps predicting physical inactivity and recommending appropriate workarounds Based on gathered information. In order to achieve life-logging and targeted healthcare improvement, wearables and multimodal interfaces are used in comparison with self-report questionnaires to create a holistic approach for the digital worker.

The real-time monitoring system of the VUM’s computational module consists of physical activity goals and recommendations which are either rule-based or predictive. Through the predictive assessment of physical inactivity, the VUM can predict steps-based physical inactivity and effectively intervene to avert cases of sedentary behaviour. As we discuss in section 3.2, by predicting days where the worker is prone to demonstrate sedentary behaviour, the physical activity monitoring system can take more proactive decisions on when and how to support the worker in remaining physically active.

Thus, the wVUMs are defined with respect to **physical, health/physiological, anthropometrics, psychometric** (i.e. personality), **behavioural, workability/goals** and **social/Quality of Life** parameters. **User interaction logs** with the A@W system are also captured in wVUM to facilitate the understanding of user behavior and his/her engagement with the A@W tools. The **wVUM Data structures** developed in the A@W Data Aggregation Module are RESTful APIs developed to support Data I/O. An overview of the design of wVUM is shown in the following figure.

Figure 1 Abstract representation of the wVUM's approach

2.2 wVUM Initialisation

During the baseline period, the wVUM asks and receives the information regarding the initialization of the personas of each worker. This initialization helps in defining the worker’s needs and industrial requirements in order to adapt technologies according to them and enhance productivity. Initial data of wVUM is used for personalizing the tools of the Ageing@Work solution at a moment when no other information is available for the workers. Thus, the information needed, is derived through questionnaires that concern either workability or health status, generally their quality of life acquired through self-reporting. This information helps in both feeding the tools offered by the project’s solution and in understanding behaviour of the workers and changes that take place through the use of these tools. The

wVUM feeds the workplace ergonomics support tool thus, anthropometric measurements are initially added in the model to facilitate customization. Moreover, it is initialized also with data regarding psychometric and behavioral information that enhance the Virtual Coach empathic behaviour.

The social and physiological information contributes in offering suggestions adapted to the social events that the worker already is fond of and also adapted to activities that the worker can do. Since we are talking about elderly workers, it is essential to keep in mind that in order to offer them suggestions for active routines, the system needs to now from the beginning any possible early signal of functional decline. All these initial data are updated with information coming from either IoT or mobile apps or questionnaires offered in specific time intervals defined in the pilot evaluation protocol of the project. Based on this updated information, the consortium examines changes and/or improvements in the workers' daily routine along with hidden patterns that justify these changes/improvements. Correlations between the initial information of the wVUM and information acquired in both the middle and the end of the pilots are necessary to be investigated for extracting useful information.

2.3 Baseline Demographic, Physiological, Psychological and Social parameters

Since the age of retirement has increased, the conditions in a workplace should be adapted in order to be ready for the ageing worker. These adaptations require changes in workplace demographics and dimensions like physiology and psychology of a worker. Flexibility in terms of these dimensions can offer workplaces ready for the ageing worker and can handle the management of the extended working life [1]. The aforementioned dimensions along with the social activity of the worker, are kept in wVUM in order to retrieve patterns and ways of facilitating ageing population in their workplaces.

The wVUM consists of data representing multiple dimensions of a worker's life so that personalized ergonomics and process services are offered in an appropriate way. Adaptation of the workplace regarding physical design is necessary along with adaptations to task assignments and scheduling. The needs of ageing workers are matched in terms of safety and health factors [2] as well, which inform the system when recommendations should be provided.

The model shown in the figure below defines the main type of data exchanged amongst the Ageing@Work components regarding demographic information and parameters that describe the anthropometric, psychological and social behaviour of the worker. The user is the core entity of the Ageing@Work database architecture which is related with all the necessary information that concern either work or personal life. Demographic data are kept for monitoring changes and adapting the workplace environment appropriately in order to achieve longer work life to ageing workforce.

Figure 2 wVUM representing demographics, anthropometrics and social parameters

Additionally, anthropometric measurements help adjusting the design of computer-aided tools and built-in ergonomic assessment with the development of digital human models [3]. Worker’s social activities and lifestyle offer a holistic approach of the life the worker leads thus, information about smoking habit [4], drug abuse (i.e. alcohol) [5] and social activities [6] are kept in different tables. In terms of this information, it is possible to detect parameters that affect daily productivity, workability and wellness. Besides, wVUM keeps track of the emotional status of the worker in case extraction of knowledge about a long-term negative emotion [7, 8] is needed.

Ageing workers may face difficulties working under conditions similar to those they worked under when they were younger, due to their physical and psychological functional decline. Hence, an analysis of their emotional status trend and information about workplace conditions that is discussed later on, may suggest a recommendation or an adaptation [9, 10] in work position or rescheduling of the tasks assigned to the worker. The basic emotions [11] stored are anger, sad, happiness, surprise, fear, disgust and no emotion but they were extended to emotional statuses in order to include stressed and tired/asleep as well. Stressed status is sensed either by face recognition or by health apps or through the smartwatch heart rate over activity. Tired status on the other hand is sensed by sleep quality measures.

Another fundamental parameter in VUM is the personality model which is kept based on the Big Five Factor model [12]. Emotional status and personality information help in the cognitive sector of the digital

worker model since they enhance the decision support system with a form of empathy. Both personality and emotion can denote more accurately how a recommendation should be served, when and why [13]. A worker who is neurotic thus may face negative feelings for a long time is one of the cases [14] where adaptations should take place.

2.4 Workability

In respect to the ageing population, workability index is used in the design of wVUM as well since methods to monitor it are of great significance lately [15]. Based on the COPSQ questionnaire mentioned in section 1.1, the wVUM stores self-reporting information about each worker’s workability and updates the records based on the Ageing@Work protocol reported in D7.2. Data analysis of the reporting done during the three distinct time intervals that are defined to evaluate workability, is going to reveal the acceptance and improvements/changes of the ageing population’s behaviour at workplaces.

In the following figure, the necessary information for evaluating workability is shown in the VUM model along with information that is related to the workplace models.

Figure 3 Information for evaluating task adaptations

As demonstrated in captured data (Figure 3), workers are assigned tasks based on multiple factors that

take into consideration their eligibility in an effort to keep productivity and satisfaction indexes to a high level. Because of the ageing workers participating in the project, VUM stores information regarding vision and/or hearing problems to assure their safety in terms of the task assigned. Apart from the functional losses, specific information about each worker’s skills and level of experience is kept along with the work field that each skill is required. Thus, for each worker both advantages and disadvantages are known in order to facilitate the appropriately automatic assignment of tasks. On the other hand, each task publishes its requirements in terms of physical demands, duration, difficulty and number of workers needed so that the system has all the necessary information. Evaluation of workers’ satisfaction and productivity defines whether adaptations and relocation or reassignment of tasks should be done. The adaptations take place by examining optimizations in scheduling based on the appropriateness of each worker for the new task.

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    <id>6</id>
  </User>
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Figure 4 User session log file from the AR Remote Guide mobile app in XML format

Moreover, productivity and wellness (out of work hours) are measured through validated questionnaires that are mentioned in section 1, and their indexes are stored in VUM offering access to information about

self-evaluation in terms of both work and quality of their life. These indexes are updated according to the validated time intervals established for each questionnaire.

To enable generation of job schedules that are compatible with workers' preferences, the job orchestration tool of the Ageing@Work platform makes use of worker related data from the wVUM. On one hand, these concern the fitness condition and capabilities in terms of skills of a worker to perform a task. Such data are the workers, the associated worker skills and skills required by each task. In addition, information regarding functional losses of the worker is acquired, in order to evaluate suitability for a task.

2.5 Productivity Enhancement

As a part of the lifelong learning, training and productivity tools the bi-directional AR-based telepresence tool that consists of the AR Remote Guide and Worker mobile applications allow on-site and remote workers to initiate and perform remote collaborative sessions in order to resolve issues that arise on the workspace. Data related to user interaction and communication using the AR Remote apps are stored in the Ageing@Work database. During each user session the mobile AR applications keep log files with information regarding the calls between the remote and on-site workers and the type of AR annotations and messages exchanged. Those data are defined by a type and a timestamp and can benefit the VUM by analysing the behaviour of the workers while using the AR apps. This way they may offer possible recommendations and ways to improve the efficiency of the interactions. An example of an AR session log containing a list of actions defined by a type, a description and a timestamp can be seen in Figure 4.

In addition, from the analysis of the AR Telepresence log files valuable information related to problems that workers experience on the workspace and the level of provided and received support and satisfaction can be derived.

In general, the concept of the Virtual Models of workers is to move a step forward from simple user profiling and use the information provided for computational intelligence as described in section 3 of this document.

2.6 Lifestyle Factors and Health Goals

Another section of VUM is implemented to store information about the goals that each worker expects to achieve through the utilization of Ageing@Work solution. As shown in Figure 5, for each work the VUM keeps data regarding health issues which address both physical and mental status. These data provide the adequate knowledge for promoting the appropriate health lifestyle recommendations. Moreover, based on the goals set by the worker, and according to rules based on international guidelines and the scientific literature, the system is able to highlight to the user those recommendations. Apart from suggestions and recommendations, the health table is used also for rearranging a worker's job task or location in the workplace, since information about musculoskeletal disorders is stored here. These disorders consist of backache and muscular pains which are highly common especially in elder workers [16], especially on those that work under hard working or environmental conditions. Meanwhile, workers' work-related stress problems and job strain are kept in VUM since they have been reported as high-level problems in

the manufacturing and mining workplaces that participate to the project based on the survey and the focus groups studied in terms of WP2. This means that these jobs are characterized by high levels of intensity which is handled once noted with relocation of the workforce.

Goals that address physical issues concern mainly adjustments at work due to bad body posture and musculoskeletal disorders while mental goals address issues that appear due to depression that may arise because of aging. Change of lifestyle factors is recommendation for achieving both physical and mental goals and includes information presented in Figure 5. Furthermore, all recommendations take into consideration the personality of the worker kept in VUM in order to enhance the system with adaptations based on the communication style that each personality profile prefers. Communication styles are separated into nurturing and challenging in order to find if there are any effects on engagement and execution of the recommendations offered.

Figure 5 Health related status and Goals

2.7 Behaviour Monitoring Parameters

During the usage of the Ageing@Work application a rich set of data, from different sources, is being collected. The data being collected are consisted of activity information from wearable devices, smartphones, and third-party apps, keystroke typing data, location information, data from medical and environmental IoT devices, and self-reports. These data periodically are sent to the server to populate the VUM and can be used to monitor the worker's behavioural aspects after modelling through the usage of machine learning or decision algorithms.

2.7.1 Sensing Modalities

An essential part of VUM's architecture is the data that are stored regarding worker's behavioural aspects, concerning the activities he does and the locations he visits during each day. The main source of these data is the Ageing@Work Data Collection Middleware, which uses the phone sensors to acquire all these different sources of information. Additionally, as complementary sources the system captures data using the smartwatch and third-party apps, such as the Samsung Health and Google Fit. The inclusion of these is valuable since they may provide additional features as well as fill in data gaps from already recorded features (e.g., worker goes for a walk without carrying his phone, instead uses only the smartwatch). *Figure 6* depicts the data being stored from the Ageing@Work application's middleware, smartwatch and third-party apps.

Figure 6 VUM sensing modalities

The formatting of the tables has the “start_time” and “end_time” as common time references, as to be able to combine information based on time periods. As such, for example, activities can be coupled with locations, providing higher level of contextuality and better modelling of user’s behaviour.

Activities information have been enriched by the Ageing@Work Middleware with the computation of Metabolic Equivalent of Task (METs) and activity’s intensity. Using these metrics, we can infer sedentary behaviour in higher granularity than with plain activity’s duration, because even if an activity has long duration it’s intensity might be low.

Table 2. Activity Data Example

<p>Example Running:</p> <pre>{ "distance": 358.3878173828125, "duration": 202854, "end": 1622566593697, "id": 354, "intensity": "Vigorous", "kcal": 38.341678619384766, "mets": 7.902907371520996, "name": "RUNNING", "start": 1622566390843,</pre>	<p>Example Walking:</p> <pre>{ "distance": 54.61859893798828, "duration": 231624, "end": 1622137547883, "id": 75, "intensity": "Sedentary", "kcal": 5.404560089111328, "mets": 1.0, "name": "WALKING", "start": 1622137316259,</pre>
---	--

<code>},</code>	<code>"steps": 479</code>	<code>},</code>	<code>"steps": 73</code>
-----------------	---------------------------	-----------------	--------------------------

Worker's location is considered sensitive information, and as such we chose to not hold any record of the exact location's latitude/longitude or address on the server. Instead, Ageing@Work application categorizes each location by the usage of an isolated dockerized API, and then sends the categorized locations to populate the VUM.

Table 3. Location Data Example

<pre> Example from Home: { "category": "HOME", "distance": 0.0, "distance_from_home": 0.0, "distance_from_work": 8815.376953125, "duration": 6778042, "end": 1622037335265, "hashedAddress": "d50e...8da20", "id": 1, "name": "HOME", "start": 1622030557223, "subcategory": "HOME" } </pre>	<pre> Example from an outdoor activity: { "category": "LANDUSE", "distance": 2178.2138671875, "distance_from_home": 69635.8125, "distance_from_work": 77994.8828125, "duration": 1104986, "end": 1622303939968, "hashedAddress": "", "id": 41, "name": "newPoint13", "start": 1622302834982, "subcategory": "NATURERESERVE" } </pre>
--	--

The worker's activities and location's categories are part the Low-Level Activity model of VUM, while a presentation of the High-Level Activity model can be seen in the "ageing_at_work_data_paths" which combines the activity with locations while the user is on the move. High level of information can be extracted for example if the worker was walking near a school to pick up his/her grandchildren, though this information should probably be enriched by additional self-reporting events.

Table 4. Path Data Example

<pre> { "activity_name": "WALKING", "category": "EDUCATION", "datetime": 1622283320535, "distance": 1360.2276611328125, "duration": 1222458, "end": 1622283199501, "hashed_address": "e41e...e590f95e", "intensity": "Light", "kcal": 73.17420959472656, "mets": 2.565354108810425, "name": "activityPOI12", "start": 1622281977043, "steps": 1818, "subcategory": "SCHOOL" } </pre>	<pre> { "activity_name": "WALKING", "category": "SOCIAL", "datetime": 1622391221963, "distance": 1699.9105224609375, "duration": 1437338, "end": 1622391097999, "hashed_address": "2152e...938b3", "id": 24, "intensity": "Light", "kcal": 93.9885025024414, "mets": 2.802457571029663, "name": "activityPOI15", "start": 1622389660661, "steps": 2272, "subcategory": "PEDESTRIAN" } </pre>
--	--

A different source of data is the included keyboard. During the usage which, the system is able to record keystroke timing related data, such as the time a key was pressed or released and Euclidian distance between consecutive keystrokes, as well as the current settings related to the vibration, sound and

keyboard size. The timing related and distance data are used to compute typing dynamics variables such as the Hold Time (HT - elapsed time between key pressure and its release), the Flight time (FT – elapsed time between the release of a key and the pressing of the next key) and other useful metrics, which are reported to be associated with cognitive impairment and psychomotor retardation. Also, the current running application, that summoned the keyboard, is recorded as to be able to infer socialization metrics, knowing that some type of apps, such as the Messenger or What’s Up, are mostly used for socialization purposes. The text input is not stored at any point of the process, respecting worker’s data privacy.

Table 5. Keyboard Data Example

```
{
  "start": 1622030529059,
  "end": 1622030545182,
  "id": 1,
  "session": {
    "currentAppName": "Messenger", "currentCountry": "GR", "currentIMEI": "dc....30", "currentLanguage": "el",
    "distance": [49.55164238720158,...16.674223302028896],
    "downtime": [1163849168,...1163861106],
    "downtimeDelete": [],
    "end": 1622050869743, "start": 1622050847463,
    "isLongPress": [0,...0],
    "isShowPopupOn": false, "isSoundOn": false, "isVibrationOn": true, "keyboardScale": 1, "numDels": 0,
    "vibrationDuration": 5,
    "pressure": [1,...1],
    "uptime": [1163849274,...1163861191],
    "uptimeDelete": []
  }
}
```

As mentioned, the VUM is populated as well from data retrieved using third party apps. An example of a Samsung Health’s payload containing heart rate, steps, floors climbed, and sleep stages can be seen below:

Table 6. Third Party Data Examples

```
{
  "samsung_health": {
    "steps": [{"count": 102, "calories": 4, "distance": 75, "start_time": 1616342940000, "end_time": 1616342999999, "unit": "count"}, ...],
    "heart_rate": [{"heart_rate": 65, "start_time": 1613390429253, "end_time": 1613390429253, "unit": "bpm"}, ...],
    "floors_climbed": [{"floors": 1, "start_time": 1617385732171, "end_time": 1617385789179, "unit": "floors"}, ...],
    "sleep": [
      {
        "start_time": 1617405540000,
        "end_time": 1617438660000,
        "sleep_stages": [
          {
            "start_time": 1617408660000,
            "end_time": 1617408720000,
            "sleep_id": 0,
            "stage": 40001, //awake
            "unit": "sleepStage"
          },
          {...}, ...],
          {
            "start_time": 1617436440000,
            "end_time": 1617438420000,
            "sleep_id": 0,
            "stage": 40004, //rem
            "unit": "sleepStage"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
}
```

```

    }, "unit": "duration"
  }
]
}
}
}

```

Some of the previously mentioned information, such as the locations and the activities, are combined in real-time within the Ageing@Work application Middleware, and a rule-based decision system triggers notifications for health & wellbeing suggestions. Some of these interventions are: breaks at work during long immobility sessions, stress relief exercises, stretching workarounds for workplace and advice for leisure walks in the nearest park. These events are stored within the “ageing_at_work_data_scenario” whereas the “name” column is the identifier of the event while the state of the intervention can be retrieved by the “event_type”, which can be either “notified”, “success” or “failed”. As such, the intervention adherence can be calculated by dividing the number of “notified” by the count of “success” events.

Except from the real-time intervention, the computational part of the VUM can also process the stored data and infer some useful interventions, which through the usage of Restful APIs can be received from the Ageing@Work application and outputted toward the user as recommendations. There are recommendations on optimized work process or daily life plans by analysing the historical data or using machine learning models. . More about the computation part of the VUM will be described in Section 3.

Table 7. Intervention Events Data Examples

<pre> { "datetime": 1622271615895, "event_type": "NOTIFIED", "id": 78, "name": "BREAK_AT_WORK" }, { "datetime": 1622275223162, "event_type": "FAILED", "id": 79, "name": "BREAK_AT_WORK" }, { "datetime": 1622275223206, "event_type": "NOTIFIED", "id": 80, "name": "BREAK_AT_WORK" }, { "datetime": 1622281632548, "event_type": "SUCCESS", "id": 81, "name": "BREAK_AT_WORK" }, } </pre>	<pre> { "datetime": 1622283094883, "event_type": "NOTIFIED", "id": 82, "name": "STAIRS" }, { "datetime": 1622283425658, "event_type": "FAILED", "id": 83, "name": "STAIRS" }, { "datetime": 1622296810197, "event_type": "NOTIFIED", "id": 84, "name": "STEPS_GOAL" }, { "datetime": 1622318401844, "event_type": "SUCCESS", "id": 85, "name": "STEPS_GOAL" }, } </pre>
---	---

2.7.2 Periodic Questionnaires

Apart from the information collected through IoT and apps, self-reports are necessary for assessing dimensions either for initializing the VUM and for enhancing the evaluation of the project’s solution with

self-reporting. A custom questionnaire regarding health and working conditions has been created by integrating/ merging validated questionnaires [17, 18, 19, 20] , to initialize some dimensions of the VUM regarding demographics, health history data, workplace performance and satisfaction, leisure time, stress levels, personalities traits and professional skills. In this questionnaire, a self-report holistic approach is achieved in the beginning of the pilot phase and before the system starts collecting information for each worker. This questionnaire is given once at the beginning and the data are kept in VUM. The questionnaire can be found in ANNEX I. Figure 7 depicts how all the different questionnaires and worker’s answers to them are stored into the database. These templated questionnaires, since they are stored as JSONs, need also to be parsed in order to retrieve the answers and calculate the score, where applicable. An example of a questionnaire answer can be seen in Table 8.

Figure 7. VUM Questionnaire Templates

Table 8. Questionnaire Answer Example

```
{
  "QuestionnaireId":2,
  "Date":"2021-04-25T12:20:52.430Z",
  "Data":{
    "Description": "(Patient Health Questionnaire-9)\nOver the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following?",
    "Name": "PHQ-9",
    "Questions":[
      {
        "id": "bc588840-6cdd-4578-a383-f86865d8f7d9",
        "QuestionType":0,
        "QuestionText": "Little interest or pleasure in doing things?",
        "QuestionDescription": "",
        "QuestionOrder":0,
        "QuestionOptions":[
          {
            "id": "d25e92cd-5eab-4f77-9012-4673b8a6a67e",
            "Description": "Not at all",
            "Points":0,
            "OptionOrder":0,
            "selected":true
          },
          {
            "id": "436e9be5-6975-4be3-929e-12e05df77852",
            "Description": "Several days",
            "Points":1,
            "OptionOrder":1,
            "selected":false
          },
          {
            "id": "a9ef2542-8819-4d37-871a-ed283c574ede",
```

```

    "Description": "More than half the days",
    "Points": 2,
    "OptionOrder": 2,
    "selected": false
  },
  {
    "id": "65479304-78ae-417a-b029-04a72f27069e",
    "Description": "Nearly every day",
    "Points": 3,
    "OptionOrder": 3,
    "selected": false
  }
]
}, ..., {...}]
}

```

2.8 Impact Assessment of Ageing@Work

In a nutshell, we will measure quality of life, acceptance, workability as outcomes in the envisaged pilot studies. We will do correlation analysis of VUM parameters with these outcomes to improve our understanding, or see statistical differences between different groups of people. Having initialized the wVUM of each worker with values taken from VUM questionnaire, see ANNEX I, the basic needs of aging workers are defined thus their study in order to address impact on workability, well-being and generally their quality of life is established. This study leads to the implementation of the Ageing@Work solution technology which is evaluated by the Ageing@Work protocol described in D7.2.

This protocol includes the validated questionnaires that measures acceptability, usability and expectations of workers regarding the technology solution offered along with questionnaires regarding quality of life, workability and well-being. These questionnaires update the wVUM with information regarding quality of life and workability after having used the project’s solutions for specific time intervals and with predefined implemented functionalities in order to notice changes and be able to define the reasons of these changes. During the impact assessment of the project, wVUM stored information can reveal changes regarding the initial state of a worker- baseline - and their state on the different measurement points. The wVUM is informed for either short-term or long-term changes of workability well-being and quality of life with the appropriate instruments defined by the consortium during the pilot planning.. The assessment instruments for the Ageing@Work platform according to D7.2 are:

- **SF-12** (Quality of Life Scale) [18]
- **COPSOQ** (Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire for Job Satisfaction) [19]
- **UTAUT** (Technology acceptance) [21]

3. Computational Part of VUM

3.1 Application's computational configuration

As mentioned in Section 2.7.1, the computational part of VUM can be either real-time, which offers event detection capabilities and health & well-being suggestions through the mobile middleware, or post-processing, which usually takes place in predefined intervals within the server.

In order to be able to configure the application's computational settings without the need of updating hardcoded values through an apk update, we have created a system that receives a configuration file, in JSON format, from the server. This file contains all the configurable settings, ranging from API URLs to variables used as conditions for the intervention rules. Before the tracking service is initialized, the application can request to retrieve the configuration file from the server, as to update the variables. The contents of this configuration file can be seen on Table 9.

Table 9. Application's dynamic configuration

Configurable Variable	Default Value	Description
URL_HTTP_LOCATION_API	Location-API-address	The location context API HTTPS address.
URL_HTTP_POST	Server-API-address	The server's http address.
HTTP_POST_HEADERS	application/json	Metadata for http requests.
AGEING_AT_WORK_PAYLOAD_URL	data/create	Endpoint to send the collected data. Combined with URL_HTTP_POST.
SEND_INTERVAL	60*60*1000	The interval, in milliseconds, at which data are being send to the server.
ALLOWS_MOBILE_DATA	false	Can application use mobile data instead of WIFI?
ACTIVITY_DETECTION_INTERVAL_IN_MILLISECONDS	15*1000	The update interval for activity detection in milliseconds.
STEP_DETECTION_INTERVAL_IN_MILLISECONDS	30*1000	The update interval for step counting reports in milliseconds.
CONFIDENCE	75	The threshold above which an activity detected is valid.
HAR_CONFIDENCE	68	The threshold above which an activity detected from the Stairs Detection Model is valid.
UPDATE_INTERVAL_IN_MILLISECONDS	30*1000	The update interval for location in milliseconds.
FASTEST_UPDATE_INTERVAL_IN_MILLISECONDS	15*1000	If other apps are also using the GPS, we can have faster updates without consuming more battery.
DESIRED_ACCURACY	HIGH_ACCURACY	The accuracy of the GPS location.
MIN_SCENARIO_TIME_OF_DAY	09	After which hour (0-24) to start the notifications.
MAX_SCENARIO_TIME_OF_DAY	21	After which hour (0-24) to stop the notification.
STILL_DURATION_TO_STOP_PATH_TRACKING	2*60*1000	How many milliseconds to wait when the detected activity is STILL, to stop the path tracking.
METERS_INTERVAL_TO_TRACK	25	The distance in meters between consecutive recordings of location during the path tracking.
LEISURE_WALK_NOTIFICATION_INTERVALS	2*60*60*1000	The interval, in milliseconds, for leisure walks notification.
EXERCISE_DURATION_TO_NOTIFY	10*60*1000	The duration of detected exercise, after which the user receives an notification informing that an exercise was detected.
EXERCISE_STEPS_PER_MINUTE	60	Steps per minute threshold to consider the current activity as an exercise and not as physical activity.
STAIRS_SCENARIO_DURATION	5*60*1000	Duration in milliseconds for which the CNN Stair recognition model runs after enabling it. If in the meanwhile no stair climbing was detected an "FAILED" event is being saved, else an "SUCCESS" one.
WALK_DURATION_AT_WORK	5*60*1000	Duration, in milliseconds, for the workers to walk during a break as to consider the intervention successful.
BREAK_AT_WORK_SCENARIO_INTERVAL	60*60*1000	The duration of continuous immobility to trigger the break@work suggestion.

STAIRS_SCENARIO_INTERVAL	8*60*60*1000	The interval, in milliseconds, at which the stair detection is triggers, upon entrance in known place (Home or Work).
BREAK_NOTIFICATION_INTERVAL	60*60*1000	The interval, in milliseconds, at which the break@work scenario suggestions are repeated.
STATIONARY_TIME_IN_MILLISECONDS	10*60*1000	The duration within an area, in milliseconds, after which if the worker is within an unknown area, this area becomes a Point of Interest (POI).
STATIONARY_TO_SLOW_DOWN_DURATION	30*60*1000	The duration, in milliseconds, of continuous immobility, after which the location tracking is being slowed-down to save battery life.
RADIUS_IN_METERS	50	The radius, in meters, which defines the boundaries of an known area.
STILL_DURATION_TO_CONGRATS	30*1000	The duration of immobility, in milliseconds, to trigger the congratulations event after a successful break@work.
HAS_PROVIDED_CONSENT	(User Defined)	Indicates the worker's consent status for sending data to the server.
EMAIL	(User Defined)	Worker's email, for authentication.
PASSWORD	(User Defined)	Worker's password, for authentication.
HOME_ADDRESS	(User Defined)	Worker's home address as given from the UI.
WORK_ADDRESS	(User Defined)	Worker's work address as given from the UI.
POI_1_ADDRESS	(User Defined)	Placeholder for additional POIS given by the worker.
KEY_ADVICE_STAIRS	(User Defined)	Option regarding the system suggestions for stair climbing.
KEY_ADVICE_BREAKS_AT_WORK	(User Defined)	Option regarding the system suggestions for breaks@work.
KEY_ADVICE_STEPS	(User Defined)	Option regarding the system suggestions for leisure walk/steps goal.
SHOULD_SHOW_EXERCISE_DETECTION	(User Defined)	Option regarding the system notifications on detected exercises.
SHOULD_WALK_MINUTES_PER_DAY	(User Defined)	Goal setting for the minimum walking minutes per day.
SHOULD_WALK_STEPS_PER_DAY	(User Defined)	Goal setting for the minimum number of steps per day.
NUMBER_OF_BREAKS_PER_DAY	(User Defined)	Goal setting for the maximum number of breaks per day.
HEIGHT	(User Defined)	Worker's height in cm. Used to calculate calories and activity intensity.
WEIGHT	(User Defined)	Worker's weight in kg. Used to calculate calories and activity intensity.

3.2 Application's Middleware Rules (Real-time)

The Ageing@Work application Middleware combines, in real-time, information from multiple modalities, such as the activity and location tracking modalities, and a rule-based decision system triggers notifications for health & wellbeing suggestions. Whenever an intervention event is triggered, an entry is stored within the phone's database, in order to be send later to the server and, as previously described, can be accessed by the "ageing_at_work_data_scenario" table whereas the "name" column is the identifier of the event while the state of the intervention can be retrieved by the "event_type", which can be either "notified", "success" or "failed".

In this Section we shall describe the rule-based logic, embedded within the Ageing@Work Application's middleware, used to either accurately collect contextual data or to output suggestions/interventions towards the workers.

3.2.1 Data collection rules/requirements

The customizable application's configuration was presented in Table 9. Using some of these variables the system is configured to collect data in specified intervals or detect activities and locations when defined thresholds are surpassed. Some of the most basic rules are presented below in pseudocode, whereas

words in italic/bold format are referring to variables mentioned in Table 9. The data collection pipelines were also described in detail, using flow diagrams, in Deliverable 4.1 Worker smart tracking infrastructure.

Table 10. Data Collection Basic Rules

<p>Rule/ Requirement: The location must be updated frequently. The system must recognize entrance and exit events from Points of Interest.</p>
<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location updates every -> <i>UPDATE_INTERVAL_IN_MILLISECONDS</i>. • Area boundary radius -> <i>RADIUS_IN_METERS</i> • Duration within area to consider Point of Interest (POI)-><i>STATIONARY_TIME_IN_MILLISECONDS</i>
<p>a) Condition (Entrance):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Current location’s distance is \leq <i>RADIUS_IN_METERS</i> from any known location) and (worker was inside a different known area) or (worker was not inside any know area). <p>a) Outcome (Entrance):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An entrance event to known POI is stored into the local database.
<p>b) Condition (Exit):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Current location’s distance is $>$ <i>RADIUS_IN_METERS</i> from any known location) and (worker was inside a known area) <p>b) Outcome (Exit):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An exit event is from previous known area is stored into the local database.
<p>c) Condition (New POI):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Current location’s distance is $>$ <i>RADIUS_IN_METERS</i> from any known location) and (worker is inside this unknown area for a duration \geq <i>STATIONARY_TIME_IN_MILLISECONDS</i>) <p>c) Outcome (New POI):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The current location is stored into the local database as a new POI. • An entrance event to this new POI is stored into the local database.
<p>Rule/ Requirement: The activities & step counter must be updated frequently.</p>
<p>Inputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity updates every -> <i>ACTIVITY_DETECTION_INTERVAL_IN_MILLISECONDS</i>. • Step updates every -> <i>STEP_DETECTION_INTERVAL_IN_MILLISECONDS</i> • Activity confidence threshold -> <i>CONFIDENCE</i>
<p>Condition:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Current activity different than the previous one) and (Current activity’s confidence \geq <i>CONFIDENCE</i>)
<p>Outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Store a Stop event for the previous activity and a Start event for the current one. • For step counter, no condition is required. Instead, every time the system gets an update on the step counter the steps are stored into the local database.
<p>Rule/Requirement: The system has to recognize POIs on the move and record related activities.</p>
<p>Inputs:</p> <p>The system combines the two previous pipelines to record locations every <i>METERS_INTERVAL_TO_TRACK</i> and activities whenever they change. The path tracking start when the system detects movement and stops after <i>STILL_DURATION_TO_STOP_PATH_TRACKING</i> milliseconds of immobility.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An array with all the recorded locations during the movement.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An array with location’s corresponding durations. • An array with all the recorded activities during the movement. • An array with activities’ corresponding durations. • <i>Area boundary radius</i> -> <i>RADIUS_IN_METERS</i> • Total duration of movement and needed duration to consider tracking valid -> <i>EXERCISE_DURATION_TO_NOTIFY</i>. • Location-categorization API -> <i>URL_HTTP_LOCATION_API</i>
Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (The total duration \geq <i>EXERCISE_DURATION_TO_NOTIFY</i>)
Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The system stores a path tracking event. The most common activity, among the activities list, categorizes the path’s activity. The center of the path is calculated as the single location that if it was considered as the center of an area with <i>RADIUS_IN_METERS</i>, the duration spent within this area would be the longest among the path. The path’s location is categorized from the most common location category among the location’s array (after being send to <i>URL_HTTP_LOCATION_API</i> for location categorization).

3.2.2 Virtual Coach Intervention’s Rules

Based on the aforementioned pipelines for the activity and location tracking, another set of rules has been developed. These rules are combining both the location and activity information, among possibly others, as to provide useful health & wellbeing suggestions, extracted from official Health Guideline Rules existing in the bibliography. Additionally, some rules might be related with the system’s requirements such as the need for the workers to answer specific questionnaires. The table below is describing this set of rules in detail.

Table 11. Virtual Coach Intervention Rules

Rule: The worker should take regular breaks to avoid long immobility sessions. (real-time)
Inputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should show advice for breaks (A) -><i>KEY_ADVICE_BREAKS_AT_WORK</i> • Current location (L) • Walking minutes over last hour (WM) • Minutes required to walk over break (MTW) -> <i>WALK_DURATION_AT_WORK</i> • Previous notifications (PN) and notification interval (NI) -> <i>BREAK_NOTIFICATION_INTERVAL</i> • Worker’s count of todays successful break events (SBC) and goal for daily breaks at work (G) -> <i>NUMBER_OF_BREAKS_PER_DAY</i>
Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (A) and (WM< MTW) and (PN\geqNI) and (SBC < G) and (L==‘WORK’ or ‘HOME’)
Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Notification suggesting taking a break to walk for 5 minutes. Store event into the local database.
Rule: The worker should reach his daily steps goal.
Inputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should show advice for step steps (A) -> <i>KEY_ADVICE_STEPS</i> • Today’s step count (S)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workers current location (L) Worker's Daily Step goal (G) -> <i>SHOULD_WALK_STEPS_PER_DAY</i> Previous notification (PN) and notification interval (NI) -> <i>LEISURE_WALK_NOTIFICATION_INTERVALS</i>
Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (A) and (S<G) and (L!= 'WORK') and (PN>=NI)
Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Notification suggesting going for a leisure walk, so as to reach the daily step goal. Store event into the local database.
Rule: The worker should take the stairs once per day.
Inputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Should show advice for stairs (A) -> <i>KEY_ADVICE_STAIRS</i> Today's stair events success (SC) Workers Location entrance events (L) Worker's Stair Climbing goal (G) Previous notification (PN) and notification interval (NI)-> <i>STAIRS_SCENARIO_INTERVAL</i>
Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (A) and (SC ==0) and (L == 'HOME' or 'WORK') and (PN>= NI)
Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Notification suggesting going by the stairs instead of using an elevator. Store event into the local database.
Rule: The has to be informed for available questionnaires to answer.
Inputs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Today's available questionnaires (Q) (retrieve from server's backend) Current time of the day (T) Latest hour of day to show notifications (MH)-> <i>MAX_SCENARIO_TIME_OF_DAY</i>
Condition: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (Q>0) and (T > MH)
Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Notification requesting to answer the available questionnaires.

3.3 wVUM Predictive Capabilities

Predictive capabilities are an essential component of the wVUM which can be utilized (e.g. by the Virtual Coach) to warn the workers about unhealthy behaviours in advance, thereby helping to prevent them and promote better overall health and lifestyle management. In addition, the ambient data collection mechanisms allow the wVUM to effortlessly exploit data from various sources and process them for the worker's benefit. A real-world example that highlights the importance of predictive capabilities is the prediction of sedentary behaviour. Through monitoring for physical inactivity, the wVUM can regularly look for patterns that reveal sedentary inclinations and effectively intervene to support the worker remain physically active.

3.3.1 Predictive Assessment for Physical Inactivity

Sedentary behavior among children and adults has become a matter of serious concern over the last decades. Recent studies have associated physical inactivity with the development of various physical and mental health issues such as obesity, cardiovascular disease, diabetes and depression. Tudor-Locke et al. [2] explore the harmful effects of prolonged sedentary behaviour on health and examine its association with low daily step counts. Even though the lack of evidence prevents them from proposing a minimum daily step count for children and adolescents, Tudor-Locke et al. define a sedentary lifestyle for adults using a threshold of 5,000 steps/day. Studies conducted by [3], [4], [5] and [6] have supported this threshold by demonstrating the effects of an abrupt transition from high to low daily step-based physical activity on healthy individuals.

The wide availability and popularity of wearable devices for physical activity tracking reinforces physical activity promotion. However, to effectively intervene and avert cases of sedentary behaviour, it is important to regularly look for patterns that reveal sedentary inclinations. Through this concept, the use of the worker dashboard is supporting the workers by facilitating the daily monitoring of their goal achievements based on the theory of self-regulation [28]. As it is evident, monitoring the daily step counts of individuals and encouraging healthy habits could potentially prevent the development of several life-threatening health issues. By predicting days where the person is prone to demonstrate sedentary behaviour, a physical activity monitoring system could be better informed beforehand and take more proactive decisions on when and how to support the user in remaining physically active.

In this vein, we introduce a machine learning approach towards the prediction of sedentary behaviour. By employing a series of machine learning algorithms, we perform classification on daily step count time series segments of fixed length that are annotated using the step count of the following day.

3.3.1.1 Related Works

So far, there have been only a handful of studies for the prediction of sedentary behaviour. In 2016, He et al. [29] introduced an autoregressive model with maximum entropy method (MEM) [8] to predict sedentary behaviour using raw activity logs from individuals. In search for the optimal parameters for their model, the research group utilized the physical activity logs of the StudentLife dataset [9]. The group determined that a person's sedentary behavior the next hour is correlated with their previous behaviours in the past six hours, and that sedentary patterns are often repeated in a daily and weekly basis.

He et al. proposed a rhythm analysis-based model [10] for the prediction and the prevention of sedentary behaviour. The model detects the rhythms of sedentary behavior and models cyclical and linear rhythms through periodic and linear functions, respectively. Again, through validating their model on the physical activity logs of the StudentLife dataset, the group was able to detect half-day rhythms, daily rhythms, weekly rhythms and biweekly rhythms among the students.

In 2019, Ozogur et al. [11] proposed a deep learning approach to the prediction of sedentary behaviour. Using a 6-hour window of historical physical activity data, the team trained a recurrent neural network (RNN) model that predicts the sedentary levels of the next hour for each student in the StudentLife dataset. After evaluating the RNN model through comparing it directly to a single neuron model, they concluded that it performs better for most students.

The aforementioned approaches focus on predicting sedentary behaviour rhythms on an hourly rather than a daily basis, and they are based on activity states. In contrast with the above works, our proposed implementation focuses on daily predictions of step-defined sedentary behaviour using objective monitoring methods, while following widely accepted physical activity recommendations. As such, we attempt to prevent sedentary behaviours a day before they occur towards encouraging individuals to become more active.

3.3.1.2 Prediction of Sedentary Behaviour Based on Daily Step Counts

For our implementation, we selected a crowd-sourced dataset [12] comprising physical activity data from several Fitbit users. For the prediction of sedentary behaviour, we utilized the daily step count data of the dataset, which consist of 31 days of logged step counts for the majority of the 33 Fitbit users included.

To maintain uniformity across the dataset, we injected the missing dates of each user log as dates that contain NaN values. Next, we removed all daily step counts under 500, as we assumed that they were not appropriately counted [13]. In addition, to balance the distribution of the data, we capped all daily step counts to a maximum of 10,000 steps, i.e. the suggested target for healthy adults [14]. To handle the missing data, we calculated the moving average of each time series in the dataset using a 7-day sliding window. After the calculation, we replaced the missing data using the corresponding values of the moving average. Any missing data that the moving average was unable to calculate were replaced using the mean value of each time series.

To approach the prediction of sedentary behaviour through exploiting the historical data of users, we converted each time series to sequences of 7 consecutive days, using a sliding window. We selected a window size of 7 to include potential weekly seasonality. Since each user's time series consists of 31 days, the resulting number of windows for each user was 24. As target data, we selected the next day for each sequence and labelled it as sedentary, if it did not surpass the 5,000 steps/day threshold, or as non-sedentary if it did.

Finally, we created a training and a test set by splitting each time series. Specifically, in the training set we included the first 14 windows and target days of each time series and in the test set we included the remaining 10 windows and target days. This way we involve all users in the training and the evaluation of our models.

We approached the prediction of sedentary behaviour as a binary time series classification problem. Thus, to classify the input sequences we examined several machine learning algorithms, one of them being Logistic Regression. We fitted a Logistic Regression model using the training set discussed in the previous subsection. In addition, due to class imbalance that resulted from the shortage of sedentary target days in the training set, we calculated the class weights using Eq.(2.1), where W_{class} is the weight of the class, S_{total} is the total number of samples, S_{class} is the number of samples of the class and n is the number of classes. Finally, we applied the class weights to the model before fitting the training data.

$$W_{class} = \frac{S_{total}}{S_{class} * n} \quad 2.1$$

Using the aforementioned training data, we additionally fitted a Random Forest model of 1,000 decision trees and an XGBoost model of 100 boosting rounds. We applied the class weights calculated using Eq. (2.1) to the Random Forest model before the training process. Similarly, before training the XGBoost model, we applied to it the ratio of the negative class samples to the positive class samples.

To examine the results of a more advanced approach, we designed a neural network consisting of two 1D convolutional layers, a flattening layer and an output dense layer of a single neuron, as shown in Fig. 8. The input convolutional layer contains 64 filters with a kernel size of 3x3 and acts as a downsampling layer by sliding the convolution window 7 elements at a time. The following convolutional layer also contains 64 filters with a 3x3 sized kernel but slides the convolution window 1 element at a time. To improve our network’s performance, we applied the ReLU activation function only to the inner convolutional layer, following the design proposed by Zhao et al. [37]. Next, we flattened the window of the inner convolutional layer and we passed the result to the dense layer, where the sigmoid activation function was applied, to transform the output to a probability.

Figure 8 The architecture of the Convolutional Neural Network

We trained the neural network using the aforementioned training set. During training, we selected a batch size of 16 samples/step and a 10% validation split. We used the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 10⁻⁴, the binary cross-entropy loss function and an early stopping mechanism. In addition, due to the imbalance between the two classes in the training data, we calculated weights for each class using Eq. (2.1) and applied them on the loss function.

To evaluate a combination of all models, we developed a Majority Vote Ensemble. The ensemble determines the output result by taking as input the labeled results of each model and counting the votes

Figure 9 The architecture of the Majority Vote Ensemble

for each class. In the case of a draw, the input is labeled as sedentary, as obtaining some false positive results is less crucial than obtaining false negative results. The architecture of the ensemble is shown in Fig. 9.

To properly evaluate the performance of our models, we tested their predictions on the remaining sequences from each user’s time series. In order to optimize each model’s results, we constructed their ROC curves on the test data and selected a probability threshold using Youden’s index [16], [39]. Next, we applied the thresholds to each model’s output probabilities to generate the labelled results. In tables I and II, we respectively present the selected probability thresholds and the sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy scores that each model achieved.

Table 12 The models’ probability thresholds

Model	Threshold
Logistic Regression	0.8687
Random Forest	0.2870
XGBoost	0.4292
CNN	0.5872

We observed that the Random Forest model achieved the highest sensitivity score but the lowest score in specificity. In contrast, the Logistic Regression model achieved the highest specificity score but the lowest sensitivity score. The XGBoost and CNN models attempted to balance their sensitivity and specificity scores, however with a noticeable incline in specificity. Finally, even though its scores did not exceed the highest measured scores, the Majority Vote Ensemble balanced the results in the most efficient manner. To further explore the performances of all models, we evaluated their predictions on an additional dataset. The dataset contained Fitbit Charge logged daily step counts from an additional user in course of 193 days. To prepare the dataset for our models, we applied the pre-processing pipeline we described in the

previous section. Furthermore, to obtain the labelled results, we applied the probability thresholds we calculated using the original test dataset. In table III, we present the sensitivity, specificity and accuracy scores that each model achieved on these additional data.

The results showed that our implementations succeeded in detecting sedentary behaviour a day earlier whenever sedentary patterns are available. In detail, the Logistic Regression model achieved the highest specificity score but the lowest score in sensitivity. The Random Forest, XGBoost and CNN models achieved quite similar results, attempting to balance both scores. And finally, the Majority Vote Ensemble achieved the highest sensitivity score, surpassing all baseline models, and a fairly high specificity score.

Table 13 The models' performance on multiple users

Model	Sensitivity	Specificity	Accuracy
Logistic Regression	0.6698	0.8929	0.8212
Random Forest	0.7547	0.8348	0.8091
XGBoost	0.6887	0.8661	0.8091
CNN	0.6981	0.8705	0.8152
Majority Vote Ensemble	0.7453	0.8571	0.8212

Table 14 The models' performance on the additional user

Model	Sensitivity	Specificity	Accuracy
Logistic Regression	0.5714	0.9051	0.8172
Random Forest	0.6122	0.8248	0.7688
XGBoost	0.6122	0.7956	0.7473
CNN	0.5918	0.8102	0.7527
Majority Vote Ensemble	0.6327	0.8175	0.7688

4. wVUM Communication Capabilities

4.1 Communication using REST APIs

The Ageing@Work framework has many different modalities, the majority of which must be able to communicate with the main server to either update the wVUM parameters or to retrieve already existing information within the database. For example, the data collection middleware might communicate to update the data collected for worker's activities or location, while the Dashboard's backend might request the worker's data aggregated by day, so as to display to the worker. Using a Representational State Transfer (REST) architecture, the framework promotes interoperability, and reinforces the communication of all the different modalities under the same rules and safety settings. The REST architecture was preferred over other options, for example Simple Object Access Protocol (SOAP), since it is easily extensible and scalable, while also provides flexibility and portability due to the independence of the server from the clients.

The tables Table 15 Store sensor data API, demonstrate some essential APIs that provide communication with the various components of the Platform.

Table 15 Store sensor data API

Call	<i>Add sensor data.</i>
-------------	-------------------------

URL	{{baseUrl}}/data/create	POST
Body	<pre> { "parameter": "string", "value": "string", "start_time": 0, "end_time": 0, "heart_rate": 0, "count": 0, "calories": 0, "distance": 0, "floors": 0, "amount": 0 } </pre>	
Response	<pre> { "message": "steps_added", "data": [{ "data_source_category_id": 2, "user_id": 4, "parameter": "steps", "value": 233, "start_time": 1594302401, "end_time": 1594302401, "has_children": 1, "updated_at": "2020-07-09 17:14:33", "created_at": "2020-07-09 17:14:33", "id": 4 }, { "data_source_category_id": 2, "user_id": 4, "parameter": "calories", "value": 132, "start_time": 1594302401, "end_time": 1594302401, "parent_data_item": 4, "updated_at": "2020-07-09 17:14:34", "created_at": "2020-07-09 17:14:34", "id": 5 }, { "data_source_category_id": 2, </pre>	

	<pre> "user_id": 4, "parameter": "distance", "value": 15, "start_time": 1594302401, "end_time": 1594302401, "parent_data_item": 4, "updated_at": "2020-07-09 17:14:34", "created_at": "2020-07-09 17:14:34", "id": 6 }], "status": 200 } </pre>
--	--

This API is used to store the worker’s sensor data in the database. The body element must include sensor-related information from the worker, such as their heart rate, sleep and sleep stages, activity events, location events, steps, distances walked or ran and more. The response consists of a detailed overview of the data that were stored in the database and an HTTP status code 200 on success.

Table 16 Get activity event duration API

Call	Get the duration of an activity for a time interval.	
URL	{{baseUrl}}/activity_events/{activity}/from/{from}/to/{to}	GET
Body		
Response	<pre> { "message": "still_data", "data": {"duration": 123456789}, "status": 200 } </pre>	

This API is used to get the duration of an activity event that happens between two given points in time for a specific worker. The activity type parameter, as well as the timestamps *from* and *to*, are mandatory. Valid activity types include staying still, walking, running, being in a vehicle', riding a bicycle, being on foot, tilting or doing an unknown activity. The response consists of the activity type, the duration in milliseconds and an HTTP status code 200 on success.

Table 17 Get location event duration API

Call	Get the duration of a location for a time interval.	
URL	{{baseUrl}}/location_events/{category}/from/{from}/to/{to}	GET
Body		

Response	<pre>{ "message": "home_data", "data": {"duration": 123456789}, "status": 200 }</pre>
-----------------	---

This API is used to get the duration of a location event that happens between two given points in time for a specific worker. The location category parameter, as well as the timestamps *from* and *to*, are mandatory. Valid location categories include accommodation, automotive, business, social, education, health, land use, public service, settlements, shop, sport, cultural, transport, workplace, home, friends, family, leisure or unknown locations. The response consists of the location category, the duration in milliseconds and an HTTP status code 200 on success.

Table 18 Get sum of steps API

Call	<i>Get the sum of steps for a time interval.</i>	
URL	{{baseUrl}}/step/from/{from}/to/{to}	GET
Body		
Response	<pre>{ "message": "step_data", "data": {"steps": 123456789}, "status": 200 }</pre>	

This API is used to get the sum of steps done between two given points in time for a specific worker. The timestamp parameters *from* and *to* are mandatory. The response consists of the summed steps and an HTTP status code 200.

Table 19 Get sleep stage duration API

Call	<i>Get the sleep stage duration for a time interval.</i>	
URL	{{baseUrl}}/data/sleep/{stage}/from/{from}/to/{to}	GET
Body		
Response	<pre>{ "message": "rem_sleep", "data": [{"duration": 123456789}], "status": 200 }</pre>	

This API is used to get the duration of a sleep stage that happens between two given points in time for a specific worker. The stage parameter, as well as the timestamps *from* and *to*, are mandatory. Valid sleep stages include being awake, light sleep, deep sleep, REM sleep, as well as the total sleep. The response consists of the sleep stage, the duration in milliseconds and an HTTP status code 200 on success.

Table 20 Get all goals API

Call	<i>Retrieve all goals for the authenticated user.</i>	
URL	{{baseUrl}}/goal	GET
Body		
Response	<pre>{ "message": "all_goal", "data": [{ "id": 1, "type": "steps", "value": 2500, "duration": "day", "user_id": 4, "created_at": "2020-06-26 16:16:47", "updated_at": "2020-06-26 16:16:47" }], "status": 200 }</pre>	

This API is used to get all worker’s goals. The response consists of the id, the goal’s type, the goal’s value, the duration, the user’s id and an HTTP status code 200 on success.

Table 21 Get personal data API

Call	<i>Get user's personal data & base demographics.</i>	
URL	{{baseUrl}}/vum/personal_data	GET
Body		
Response	<pre>{ "message": "personal_data_base_demographics", "data": { "NickName": null, "Gender": null, "Email": null, "City": null, "Country": null, "PostalCode": null, "DateOfRegistration": null, "Language": null, } }</pre>	

	<pre> "Photo": null, "BirthDate": null, "LevelOfEducation": null, "LivingStatus": null, "WorkingSince": null, "BSC": null, "MRS": null, "WBS": null, "WorkingPosition": null, "IncomeObj": null, "IncomeSub": null, "IncomeContributor": null, "DependentPersons": null, "OccupationalStatus": null }, "status": 200 } </pre>
--	---

This API is used to get the worker's personal data and base demographics. The response consists of various personal information regarding the worker, such as their gender, email, city, country, birth date, level of education, working position, income and more. It returns an HTTP status code 200 on success.

Table 22 Get anthropometrics data API

Call	Get user's anthropometrics data.	
URL	{{baseUrl}}/vum/anthropometrics	GET
Body		
Response	<pre> { "message": "personal_data_base_demographics", "data": { "Weight": null, "Height": null, "BodyFat": null, "Stature": null, "WaistCircumference": null, "SittingHeight": null, "HeightFromFloorToTopOfKneeWhenSitting": null, "HeightFromSittingSurfaceToTopShoulders": null, "ShoulderElbowLength": null, "ForearmHandLength": null, "HipBreadth": null, "FootLength": null, "FootBreadth": null, </pre>	

```

"StepLength": null,
"StepWidth": null,
"StrideLength": null,
"StepsPerTwoMinutes": null,
"bmi": null
},
"status": 200
}

```

This API is used to get the worker’s anthropometrics data. The response consists of various anthropometrics-related information regarding the worker, such as their height, weight, body fat, BMI, sitting height, step length, step width and more. It returns an HTTP status code 200 on success.

Table 23 Get health data API

Call	<i>Get user's health data.</i>	
URL	{{baseUrl}}/vum/health	GET
Body		
Response	<pre> { "message": "vum_health_data", "data": { "GeneralHealth": null, "SicknessAbsence": null, "SubjectiveCardiorespiratoryFitness": null, "ObjectiveCardiorespiratoryFitness1": null, "ObjectiveCardiorespiratoryFitness2": null, "MusculoskeletalDisorders": null, "OtherChronicDiseases1": null, "OtherChronicDiseases2": null, "PhysicalFatigue": null, "ChronicFatigue": null, "NegativeFeelings": null, "Depression": null, "DepressionResearcherNotes": null, "SubjectiveStress": null, "Concentration": null, "Attention": null, "Memory": null, "SubjectiveSleepQuality": null, "ObjectiveSleepQuality": null, "ObjectiveStress1": null, "ObjectiveStress2": null, "Feelings": null, </pre>	

```

"BodyTemperature": null,
"BloodGlucose": null,
"HeartRate": null
},
"status": 200
}

```

This API is used to get the worker’s health data. The response consists of various health-related information regarding the worker, such as their general health, absences due to sickness, concentration, attention, memory, body temperature, heart rate, musculoskeletal disorders, mental health status and more. It returns an HTTP status code 200 on success.

Table 24 Get lifestyle data API

Call	<i>Get user's lifestyle data.</i>	
URL	{{baseUrl}}/vum/lifestyle	GET
Body		
Response	<pre> { "message": "vum_lifestyle_data", "data": { "Smoking1": null, "Smoking2": null, "FruitsVegetablesPortions": null, "Alcohol": null, "Water": 2, "PhysicalActivityLeisureTime": null }, "status": 200 } </pre>	

This API is used to get the worker’s surveyed lifestyle data. The response consists of lifestyle information regarding the worker, such as if they are smoking, drinking alcohol, as well as their fruit and vegetable consumption levels, water intake and their leisure time. It returns an HTTP status code 200 on success.

5. Virtual Workplace Models

The Ageing@Work workspace entity contains attributes describing the establishment of a virtual models for both factories and domestic workplaces. These workplace models can be used for simulation-based assessment of a working task and ergonomics optimization (T3.4). Moreover, they provide the necessary model structures and definitions for the development of VR and AR based learning tutorials and training applications (T6.2). The complete Virtual Workplace Model schematic and the interconnection with other

components of the Ageing@Work platform is illustrated in Figure 10 and explained briefly below. More details are provided in the subsequent sections.

Figure 10 Virtual Workplace Model schematic

3D Model describes the 3D mesh data modelled/scanned and used in several Ageing@Work modules. This data can be represented as a group of meshes or a point cloud, depending on the application. The 3D model sub meshes can be extended through **semantic** data instances holding information about the interactions performed in simulations and XR training (to support task T6.2). **Simulation** holds distinct data and semantics used in a framework we have developed (*3D Simulator*) to provide the necessary functionalities and authoring tools for the simulation of working tasks, based on the created models of machines and surrounding workplace environment. The DHM (Digital Human Model) instance is connected to virtual worker model (T3.2 – VUM), which provides all necessary personalized information (e.g. anthropometric data of the worker) to allow the development of a digital twin. This digital twin can be used to simulate real world scenarios (processes, tasks and actions) with different setups introduced in different layouts. The DHM interaction data is analysed directly in the Unity Simulation Framework through calculation of the RULA scores, or extracted to external biophysics assessment modules (e.g., OpenSim). **Environmental factors** represent environmental data provided by different sensors placed inside the workspace environment. The physical aspects of a workspace have a direct impact on productivity, health, concentration, and safety of the workers, so a **thermal environment** assessment (air temperature, air velocity, humidity, mean radiant temperature, metabolic rate and thermophysical properties of clothing) needs to be tracked and analyzed constantly. Work environments contain

significant exposures that can affect the health of occupants during their activities. So too does the need for research into the circumstances that make exposures more likely and the effectiveness of interventions to reduce the exposures [40]. **Noise** levels in the workspace, even if they are low, can cause distraction [41] or chronic health effects [42] and accidents [43]. **Luminance** and light temperature levels can affect many biological functions such as sleep and can influence a worker's mood and level of alertness [44] and performance [45]. **Heat exposure**, even in tropical and subtropical countries cumulatively with several industries with high temperature factories (glass, steel, iron, mines) can cause heat stress and have a negative impact on worker efficiency [46]. When working in hot and **humid** environments, the physiological parameters such as heart rate, body temperature, blood pressure and sweat production will obviously change, depending also on the work intensity [47].

5.1 Geometry Layer

The geometry layer represents all types of 3D geometries of the VWM ranging from the factory indoor space to the furniture, tools and machinery used. All these 3D shape representations of the objects are created through classic methods (e.g., CAD software) and modern methods (3D scans and processing). The 3D geometry layer consists of the virtual prototypes of real-life 3D objects, that will, in the future, be used in various types of simulations aiming to recreate real-life operation conditions. This layer does not provide any semantic information about the 3D object themselves, such as ergonomic factors, interaction details, physics etc. but only provide the visual representation of the workspace objects. This section presents the methods used for the creation/acquirement of 3D objects used during T3.3.

5.1.1 3D Modelling

The aggregate of objects, that can be found in a workspace, lie within the range of the complexity of their geometry, also considering the level of detail needed for each specific use case. Despite the impressive results offered by 3D scanning technologies and processing methods for the denoising, repair of the 3D objects acquired, sometimes the level of detail or the simplicity of the 3D object points to the use of a CAD /3D software. Following the computer processing evolution, 3D modelling software has diversified into specialist tools for creating prototype products, visual effects, simulation, and other design features that are good across several industries, including architecture, interior design, landscape design, animation,

visual effects etc. Most of the software shares the basic functionalities such as mesh and surface modelling, texture wrapping, simulations, sculpting, rigging, and rendering.

Maya by Autodesk is a 3D animation, modelling, simulation and rendering program, which is mainly used for cinema or animation projects. This advanced 3D software is also great for character creation, virtual reality, and animations. Its vast feature set includes particles, hair, solid body physics, cloth, fluid simulations and character animation. *Maxon's Cinema 4D* has been around for many years and is highly regarded in the worlds of motion graphics, visualization, and illustration. It is a professional, complex piece of software, known for its overall stability and for being the 3D modelling software with the easiest learning curve. *3DS Max* by Autodesk offers a robust 3d modelling toolset, rich set of plugins, and can handle a wide variety of file formats. 3DS Max is Autodesk's PC-only 3D computer graphics program, used for TV and feature film production and for architectural and product visualization. Like Maya, 3DS Max boasts a very robust toolset for 3D modelling, including fluid simulations, hair, cloth, plus character rigging and animation.

Figure 11 From top left to down right : (a) Original Model . (b)Unity3D model. (c,d) Blender model

Even though the software solutions represent the industry standards, all require commercial licenses that may range between 1000\$ to 4500\$. Considering the stability and flexibility provided the subscription price of these solutions is not prohibitive. However, lots of free available software can provide the necessary tools a 3D modeler/designer needs, to achieve competing results to this effect. The most acknowledged free 3D software is Blender by Blender Foundation, an open-source 3D creation suite. It supports the entirety of the 3D pipeline—modelling, rigging, animation, simulation, rendering, compositing and motion tracking, video editing and 2D animation pipeline. Blender may lack some features offered by commercial software, but as an open-source software is constantly upgraded and has a very active community of developers. To this end, a designer can program his own tools and loads extra plugins to Blender in order to customize the software to his needs.

In the scope of the Ageing@Work project, we developed three 3D geometry models, in cooperation with ANEFA and Siemens partners. These models were then used either in virtual training scenarios, workspace simulations and ergonomic analysis with certain tools. The models are:

1. ALZMETAL Alztronic 9

This model represents a drilling machine used in Siemens factories. Based on a technical with the dimensions of this machine, we created a virtual prototype containing the important parts such as the dimensions and the semantics of the interactive parts. This model was then used in our Unity simulation framework containing all the important steps of certain tasks performed with the drilling machine. As this simulation was followed by an ergonomic analysis the precision on this specific 3D model was a necessity. However, some interactive parts such as levers and buttons, used in XR training scenarios were scaled properly, in order to provide a satisfying user experience. The impact of this discontinuity between the actual machine and the virtual prototype is not crucial for the simulation results, nor is for the ergonomics assessment.

2. Caterpillar 336 & 972

In the same manner, two Caterpillar excavators used by ANEFA, were modelled with the use of Blender. The models were meant to be used for ergonomic analysis so the necessary part to be modelled was only the interior cabin of each excavator.

Figure 12 Caterpillar 972 interior cabin 3D model

Figure 13 Caterpillar 336 interior cabin 3D model

5.1.2 3D Scanning

3D scanning is a technique used to capture the shape of a real-world object using a 3D Scanning device. These devices use several technologies depending on the object or space being scanned. **Photogrammetry**

is a technique where, a set of photos is taken from an object, from different perspectives and then analyzed from special software, identifying identical characteristic points of the objects in each image. Through this analysis, a point cloud is extracted which then can be transformed into a 3D mesh. **Structured light** devices project structured patterns of light (parallel grids or geometric patterns) onto the scanned object. The analysis of the deformation of these patterns onto the object, leads to the 3D reconstruction of digital copy of the original one. **Time-of-flight (ToF)** scanners use a laser source and project one or more beams onto the object. The scanner can calculate the distance of each point, by measuring the time traversed by the laser beam after bouncing on the object and returning to the receiver. A similar operation in laser scanners is by using **triangulation**, where the device uses a laser and a receiver to measure distance by trigonometry. In the scope of the Ageing@Work project, we scanned several spaces such as a Siemens factory floor and a relais adjustment machine used at this factory.

Figure 14 Siemens Factory Floor

We imported the relais scan point cloud into MeshLab, cleaned it and removed the outliers and segmented it as Figure 15 shows. We estimated the normal of each segmented point cloud and reconstructed the meshes. The result as well as a prototype with simple geometries for future use in Unity can be seen in Figure 16.

Figure 15 Relais Workspace original scan and segmented scan

Figure 16 The reconstructed meshes and the final prototype

5.1.3 Geometry Processing Tools

5.1.3.1 Automatic Floor Extraction Tool

For the floor map extraction of a point cloud, several processing steps were performed. We used RANSAC to detect the primary plane of the point cloud, which we assumed to coincide with the floor plane. This weak assumption is very often used in floor detection algorithms. The primary plane is then used for calculating the rotation and translation needed for the point cloud to fall flat on the $y=0$ plane. After this step, we apply a height threshold to differentiate between the points that belong to the floor or with everything else. The result of our processing so far is shown in Figure 17,, with blue describing the floor points and red the rest of the point cloud.

Figure 17 Application of the height threshold

A lot of holes are introduced to the point cloud from the LiDAR device. To improve upon our estimation, a processing step is performed on the extracted floor points, where we search for gaps (assuming we know the dimensions of the gaps left by the LiDAR) and we fill them with points. An example of before and after the hole filling is shown in Figure 18. While we extracted the floor points, they are not all traversable.

Figure 18 Application of hole filling

This is because objects that hover above the ground can potentially impede movement and act as obstacles. For example, the floor below a table is partially scanned by a LiDAR and the points are classified as floor points, but they may not be traversable (depending on the height of the operator). For this reason, in order to filter out the non-traversable regions of the map, we construct a grid like map, where each grid has fixed dimensions and the map spans the entire spatial space of the point cloud. Each grid that contains at least

one floor point is marked as “potentially traversable”. Afterwards, for each such grid we check whether it contains enough non-floor points below a certain height (the height can be tweaked to match the height requirements of the application). If the threshold is not reached, then the grid is marked as “traversable” or otherwise the grid is removed from the map. After this step, we are left with only traversable floor points. Lastly, we compute a mesh of the traversable floor points. For this we down sample the point cloud and we perform a Delaunay triangulation to get the mesh. The final results are depicted in Figure 19.

Figure 19 Final result of the floor extraction algorithm

5.1.3.2 Image based 3D mesh denoising through a block matching 3D CNN filtering approach.

Despite the impressive results of recent 3D mesh denoising [48-50] algorithms that are used in the area of image processing continue to inspire the area of 3D mesh processing. Motivated by this observation, we focus on converting the problem of mesh to image denoising using very robust approaches that have been used and successfully tested in this area. 3D transform-domain CF (e.g., 3D block matching - BM3D [51]) is an approach that achieves state-of-the-art image denoising performance by providing a 3D estimation that consists of jointly filtered grouped image blocks. CF is a special procedure that deals with 3D groups formed by similar 2D fragments of the image, including the following steps: 3D transformation of a group, shrinkage of the transform spectrum, and inverse 3D transformation. The CF of the grouped blocks reveals the details which are common between blocks, since for each pixel, we obtain several different estimates that need to be combined. This method has been successfully applied in many applications including image/video denoising [52, 53] deblurring, superresolution, and compression. CF approaches process the noisy images by successively extracting reference blocks and by matching blocks that are similar to the reference one, forming a 3D group matrix. After performing a 3D transform to the group formed by the overlapping blocks and attenuating the noise by hard thresholding, an aggregation step is taking place in order to form the estimate of the whole image. Recent approaches [54] suggest substituting the 3D transform-domain processing with traditional CNNs, outperforming the original BM3D approaches in terms of computational efficiency. The BM3D filtering of images and its adoption to meshes have an intuitive formulation, which leads to a simple data-driven method that addresses issues that stem from

the two dimensions to manifolds in three dimensions. The data-driven methods have some significant benefits as compared to the traditional mesh denoising methods [55-57], since they do not require the searching of ideal values per parameter for each model. However, their limitations mainly rely on the large dataset, required for the training process, and the corresponding training complexity. Additionally, in real case scenarios, the testing data have generally a different form from the training data (due to different light conditions, device characteristics, etc.) making the implementation of the CNN process in real applications, to be problematic. A possible solution to this problem is to remove any objective characteristic from the data (i.e., training and testing), in order to be independent of geometry constrains (density, connectivity, etc.), different quality of the scanner devices, or other external conditions that could affect the captured 3D model.

Considering the state-of-the-art methods and the aforementioned drawbacks, we developed a novel pipeline for 3D mesh denoising that efficiently exploits the benefits of the 3D transform domain CF, used for image denoising. The main contributions of the proposed method are:

- The proposed data-driven method gives the flexibility for fully automatic runtime execution, without the need for exhaustive searches of ideal parameters per model.
- Our method has no special requirements, related to the form of the 3D mesh, since it operates with equal-sized images uniformly, encoding the useful geometrical information of any mesh.
- The proposed image-based approach results in a more efficient training process, avoiding the need for large datasets, exploiting efficiently geometrical coherence.
- We show how a method, inspired by robust and well-known approaches used in the area of the image processing, can be also efficiently used in the area of 3D mesh processing.

Figure 20 Pipeline of the proposed method for image-based 3D mesh denoising using BM3D CNN filtering

Preprocessing

The most significant process is a pre-processing step that generates the appropriate and uniformly used form of the equal-sized images which efficiently encode the geometrical information of any noisy mesh. Figure 20 briefly illustrates the pipeline of the proposed schema. We work with triangle meshes consisting of vertices and faces. A noisy mesh can be represented as the sum of the original mesh vector with a noise vector. Each face of the mesh is represented by its corresponding normal and centroid point. Each unit centroid normal corresponds to a RGB pixel p_i . However, a pixel of an image cannot take negative values, so for this reason we normalize the values of the normals. Then, we link the RGB components of each pixel

to the centroid normals, respectively. In this way, we can represent the normals through pixels intensities, which is a fundamental concept in our approach.

Creation of images based on normals.

We start assuming that for each centroid point there is a patch which is created based on its proximity with the geometrical nearest neighbouring centroids. Then, we estimate the normals of the corresponding faces and we formulate an image with size depending on the neighbouring centroids. In the central cell of the first row, we place the “normal-of-interest” (in red colour). The normal n_{12} of the closest centroid (i.e., d_1) is placed in the first right cell, then the normal n_{13} of the next closest centroid (i.e., d_2) is placed in the first left cell, and the completion of the row continues, in turn, using the normals of all centroids in a descending order. The next i rows are completed in the same manner assuming, however, that the central cell represents the normal of the i closest centroid of n_1 , increasingly for each row.

Creation of the dataset consisting of ideal images.

Image-guided filtering has been presented in many papers providing superior results [58-60]. In our method we follow the same guidelines as guided normals algorithms [61-63] but using guided pixels and ideal-selected images, for the filtering step of the mesh denoising. As we discussed earlier, for each centroid normal of the mesh, we estimate an image, the first row of which represents the nearest neighbourhood area called “patch”. Nevertheless, the same pixel may be presented in more than one row/patch since each neighbourhood area is overlapping the neighbouring areas of other normals. In fact, some of these rows may better represent the “color” of a pixel. For this reason, we collect a set candidate rows and our main objective is to find which one, is the ideal representative of the pixel [64], in terms of the similarity of the colour. For each one of these candidate rows, we estimate the corresponding covariance matrix, and we decompose it to its eigenvector and eigenvalues. For the estimation of the ideal-selected row, we investigate two parameters: (i) the Euclidean norm of the first 2 eigenvalues, (ii) the maximum colour difference between the current pixel and the other pixels of the same rows. Finally, the guided pixel is estimated as the average pixel of the ideal-selected row. More information on this methodology can be found in our published work.

For the creation of the ideal images, we follow the procedure described above, but using the guided pixels instead of the normals. In Figure 21, we present examples of images created by the RGB representation of: (i) the normals, and (ii) the guided pixels, for different features (i.e., flat area, edge and corner) of Fandisk model affected by different level of Gaussian noise. As we can observe, the images, created by the guided pixels (Figure 21-(ii) (b)-(d)), have a similar presentation with the original, despite the different levels of noise. On the other hand, images that have been created using the centroid normals are very noisy and differ from the original, making difficult to be denoised, even in cases of flat areas. This observation is very important since it shows that it is not necessary to train different models for different noise patterns, as other data-driven methods do. Instead, a generic model would be also sufficient. This is especially useful in cases where the level or type of noise is not known a-priori.

BM3D CNN for ideal images denoising and our method

BM3D uses three basic steps:

- **Block matching** which tries to find groups of similar patches,
- **3D wavelet shrinkage** which denoises each one of these groups in the 3D wavelet transform domain.
- **Patch group aggregation** is an averaging procedure in which all the estimated patches return to their original positions reweighed each pixel appearing in many instances since images are created by overlapping patches [65]

For a more efficient block matching step, we use a feature classification, similar to the study implemented in [66]. More specifically, we classify each centroid into three different categories of features (i.e., flat area (F), edge (E) and corner (C)), using a k-means ($k = 3$) clustering, applied to the vector of its eigenvalues. To create a more relevant dataset, we rotate all normals of each patch about a calculated angle, as shown in Figure 22, so that the “normal-of-interest” (i.e., lied in the red face), to be equal to the constant vector $[1 \ 0 \ 0]$. In this way, a more coherent dataset is created, accelerating the learning process. Otherwise, patches with every possible normal direction would need to be provided, resulting in the creation of very large training dataset, also increasing the execution time of the learning step.

Our presented CNN (Figure 23), similar to [54], represents the second step of the BM3D (i.e., 3D wavelet shrinkage) and consists of two convolution layers and a nonlinear transform layer. More specifically, the first convolution layer is used as the wavelet transform step and the second as the inverse wavelet transform step. The nonlinear transform layer is used as the wavelet shrinkage step. Similar to [54], the radial basis functions (RBFs) is used instead of regular hard thresholding or Rectified Linear Unit (ReLUs).

After the estimation of the denoised pixels, which is the central pixel of the first row of the denoised images, we convert the RGB values to the values of the corresponding denoised centroid normals. Then, we reconstruct the denoised mesh updating its vertices, using the robust and well-known equation of [66].

Figure 21 Images of 25x25 pixels, representing patches of different features, affected by different level of noise: (a) original model, (b) $\sigma_E = 0:2$, (c) $\sigma_E = 0:4$, (d) $\sigma_E = 0:6$. The images are created: (i) using normals and (ii) using the guided pixels

Figure 22 Example of patch rotation.

Figure 23 Patches of the mesh are converted to images and then they are fed into the CNN for denoising.

Experimental Analysis and results

The experiments were carried out using an Intel Core i7-4710 CPU @ 3.60GHz PC with 16 GB of RAM. For the experiments, a variety of 3D meshes were used [67], affected by different levels of noise. For the training process, we use only 5 different models, consisting of ~ 1.2 million (M) centroid points in total. This means that we have 1.2 M very relevant instances for the training which seem very effective, according to the experimental results. For the evaluation of the reconstructed results, we use the following metrics:

- (1) The average one-sided Hausdorff distance HD from the denoised mesh to the known ground-truth mesh.
- (2) The metric θ representing the average angle difference between the normals of the ground truth and the reconstructed model.
- (3) Heatmap visualization highlighting, in different colours, the difference between original and reconstructed mesh.

The quality performance of the proposed technique is compared with other well-known and robust techniques of the literature (a, b, c, d, e) but also some data driven methods (f, g), namely:

- a) Non-iterative smoothing (NIS) [68]
- b) Fast and effective (FAE) [66] mesh denoising
- c) Bilateral normal filtering (BNF) [69]
- d) Guided normal filtering (GNF) [62]
- e) Two-stage graph spectral processing (TSGSP) [64]

- f) Deep autoencoders denoising (DAD) [70]
- g) Cascade normal regression [67]
 - a. by using only a small dataset of models (CNR) (the exact same dataset used)
 - b. by using a larger dataset (CNR+)

Our method is denoted as (OUR) and (GEN OUR) represents our approach but using a general training model, having been trained by different levels of noise at the same time. In Figure 26, we present the original and three corresponding noisy 3D models which have been affected by three different level of noise. We provide enlarged details of each reconstructed model, for easier comparison among the methods, and we also provide the metric. The benefits of our approach are more apparent when the level of noise is **greater than 0.3**. For a lower level of noise, the results are comparable with those of the other methods. We can make similar conclusions observing the heatmaps of Figure 25, which visualize in different colours the differences between the reconstructed and original mesh, in three different levels of noise. Big differences are represented by red colour while small differences are represented with blue. Finally, in Figure 24, we present plots of HD error per different level of noise, for the reconstructed models of different approaches. For a fairer comparison between data-driven and other conventional methods, we set fixed values at the parameters, which provide good results in all levels noise, and we do not search for the ideal values per each parameter and model. Our method avoids the over-smoothing of the models and at the same time, preserves the special characteristics of the features.

Figure 24 Hausdorff distance error for different levels of noise

Figure 25 Heatmaps of (a) NIS, (b) FAE, (c) BNF, (d) GNF, (e) TSGSP, (f) DAD, (g) CNR, (h) CNR+, (i) OUR GEN, (j) OUR

Figure 26 Denoising results of: (a) NIS, (b) FAE, (c) BNF, (d) GNF, (e) TSGSP, (f) DAD, (g) CNR

5.1.3.3 Fast Mesh Denoising with data driven normal filtering using deep variational autoencoders.

Figure 27 Pipeline of the proposed approach

Figure 28 CVAE architecture and training scheme. Normal coordinates of noisy and noise-free patches are employed. Initially, they are properly rotated and labeled with k-means clustering.

Auto-encoder architecture for 3D mesh denoising

Training data were generated from meshes, distorted by noise, using the normal vectors corresponding to the 3D mesh faces. After training the autoencoder, the generated output vector is used for a normal-based vertex update [69] of the mesh vertices. Specifically, a conditional variational autoencoder [71] was employed, as illustrated in Figure 28. A conditional Gaussian encoder with two dense layers is succeeded by a conditional Bernoulli decoder with two dense layers. Each dense layer is succeeded by a layer of ReLUs and a dropout layer.

Training and Denoising

This section presents the autoencoder training and denoising pipeline, depicted in Figure 27 and Figure 28 and the patch descriptor utilized in the proposed scheme.

Patch Descriptor

The patch descriptor aims to constrain the latent space, to allow for efficient training of the autoencoder. Assuming a local coordinate system, arranging faces constrains the latent space in the z-axis. To further constrain the latent space across x and y axes the patch is rotated by a calculated angle in order to match a known arbitrarily defined vector. The motivation behind rotating each patch towards the same direction is that it allows efficient training with smaller training sets. Otherwise, we would have to include patches with every possible direction of normals to the training dataset, resulting in large datasets.

Training

The training of the deep network is schematically presented in Figure 27 and Figure 28. The training set contains pairs of noisy and noise-free patches comprised of N neighbouring faces. The corresponding face normals are rotated around a rotation axis. For the definition of the rotation axis the normals of the noisy patch are used as reference. In order to generate labels for the training set, we perform K-means clustering defining the group centroids for K clusters. The motivation behind applying K-means clustering is that it divides the dataset into groups of patches with high curvature, low curvature, flat areas, and features i.e.

corners. Thus, different models are trained for each category. Figure 29 presents an example of a 3D mesh and its corresponding noisy version. The K-means clustering of the different surface categories is depicted using different colour per different cluster. The coordinates of the normalized normal vectors are normalized as well, and the matrix of the vectors of the coordinates is reshaped. Finally, the training is performed with Adam optimizer.

Figure 29 Visualization of the K-means clustering for a (a) noise-free, and (b) a noisy mesh of the same model.

Denoising

The denoising process is visualized in Figure 27. To use the trained autoencoder for denoising, patches are formed on the noisy mesh. For each patch, the average normal is extracted and the patch is rotated so that the average normal is co-directional to the known arbitrarily defined vector, to form the input matrix. After the autoencoder has generated the filtered output, they are reshaped back to their original form. The exported filtered normal vector for every patch is the first column of the reshaped original matrix input. Finally, each patch is rotated by the opposite angle and the same axis, that they were rotated with in the first place.

Figure 30 Hyper-parameter optimization radar chart

Post Processing

As a final post processing step, we use the bilateral filtering approach according to [69]. Finally, using the denoised normals we update the vertices according to [50].

Experimental Analysis and Results

Two different datasets are examined. The first includes meshes originating from the shape repository of the AIM@Shape project [72] with synthetic Gaussian noise. The second utilizes Kinect 2 scans of 3D printed objects provided by [67]. The latter provides noisy scanned outcomes along with ground truth models. To test the denoising capability of our method, we compared our results to guided mesh normal filtering [62], bilateral normal filtering [69], L_0 minimization mesh denoising [73], fast and effective mesh denoising [66], mesh denoising via cascaded normal regression [67] and feature preserving mesh denoising based on graph spectral processing [64]. As an additional comparison, the CVAE part of our pipeline was replaced with traditional autoencoders, referred to as AE. For the latter, a 5-layer deep autoencoder was employed with $N = [256 \ 128 \ 64 \ 128 \ 256]$ the number of neurons for each layer. An element-wise sigmoid operation succeeds each layer, trained with a mean square error loss function.

- Synthetic Gaussian Noise:

Eight meshes were selected for the training of the autoencoder architecture, comprising in total of 1,977,740 patches. Noisy meshes were synthesized by adding Gaussian noise $N \sim (0, 0.1 L_p)$ co-directional to each vertex normal. 1,977,740 training pairs of noisy and noise-free rotated patches were utilized for the training of the autoencoder. Two configurations were tested for patch size, $n = 8$ and $n = 20$ neighbors. $K=200$ was selected for the K-means clustering of the CVAE. Training was performed with an Adam optimizer with $\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$ and $\epsilon = 1e-8$. The training took place for 100 epochs, utilizing an NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 graphics card with 8GB VRAM and compute capability 6.1. For the bilateral filtering, we execute only $N_B=1$ iteration, while for the vertex update operation, we execute $N_B=20$ iterations. Experimental evaluation showed that for noise level up to $N \sim (0, 0.1 L_p)$ a single bilateral iteration adequately performs fine-tuning, by removing small artifacts, while more iterations increase the computational cost without any additional benefit.

- Kinect Scans:

Kinect scans were selected from the dataset provided by [67] in order to form 927541 training examples in total. The trained CVAE model was employed to denoise a noisy Kinect scanned model excluded from the training set. The observed noise level of the Kinect scans was computed to $N \sim (-0.18, 1.4L_p)$, while Figure 33 presents the denoising outcome. Furthermore, different settings were tested to evaluate optimal patch size and number of bilateral iterations. Patch size ranged in $n = [8, 20, 40, 60]$, the number of clusters in $K = [6, 10, 50, 100, 200]$ and the number of bilateral filtering iterations N_B in $N_B = [0, 1, 4, 8]$.

- Hyper parameter optimization:

To define the number of nodes for each layer we performed hyper-parameter optimization. For encoding layers E_1 , E_2 and decoding layers D_1 , D_2 the number of nodes ranged in $N_{E1}, N_{E2}, N_{D1}, N_{D2} \in [256, 512, 1024, 2048, 4096]$. The number of clusters was set equal to $K=200$, the patch size $n=20$, the learning rate ranged in $lr \in [1e-05, 2e-05, 3e-05]$, and the keep ratio ranged in $kr \in [0.90, 0.95, 0.99]$. We computed the set of parameters that exhibit higher performance, in terms of lower ELBO loss, as shown in Figure 30. i) Batch size equals 256 ii) keep ratio $kr = 0.99$, iii) learning rate $lr = 3e-05$, iv) decrease ratio $dr = 0.998$, v) $NE1 = 2048$, vi) $NE2 = 2048$, vii) $ND1 = 2048$ and viii) $ND2 = 2048$.

- Evaluation models and metrics:

The quality of the reconstructed results is evaluated using a) the Hausdorff distance (HD) which represents the average one-side distance between the reconstructed and the original 3D mesh, b) the metric α which represents the average angle difference between the normals of the ground truth and the reconstructed model c) visualizations which present in different colours the absolute difference between the reconstructed and original meshes.

Mesh denoising studies

- Evaluation of reconstructed models:

In our work we evaluated the Hausdorff distance and the mean angular difference α of the face normals between original and denoised 3D models correspondingly. We used a variety of different initialization approaches and architectures [62, 64, 66, 67, 69, 73]. More specifically, we deployed two different deep architectures i.e., AE and CVAE), in two different patch sizes (i.e., with 8 and 20 nearest neighbours (nn)), and with, or without post-processing step (pp).

Figure 31 Denoising results using: (a) AE, (b) CVAE

The best performance depends on the model, and none of these approaches is universally the best. Nevertheless, in most of the cases, the CVAE using 8 nearest neighbours seem to have the most stable behaviour. Comparing the reconstructed meshes provided by AE and CVAE, we notice that simple AE gives a smoothed result to the object's surface, but it negatively affects the preservation of features. On the other hand, CVAE achieves the accurate reconstruction of geometrical features, but the surface of flat areas contains artifacts, as shown in Figure 22. However, this is a problem efficiently tackled by the post-processing step.

Figure 32 Denoising results and normal angle difference visualization between reconstructed and original 3D model with Gaussian noise $N \sim (0,0.1lp)$. For each model absolute distance (upper colored mesh) and theta distribution (lower colored mesh) are presented. (a) original mesh, (b) noisy mesh, (c) fast and effective, (d) bilateral normal filtering, (e) L0 minimization, (f) guided normal filtering, (g) Cascaded mesh denoising (h) our approach.

Figure 32 presents a visual comparison of the reconstructed models. In this figure, we also provide enlarged details as well as the α metric for easier evaluation. Additionally, Figure 32 illustrates a

visualization of the absolute distance and the theta metric between the original and the reconstructed model for each vertex of the meshes. The lowest value (dark blue) denotes that the compared vertices have the same position, in the 3D coordinate system, while a high value (dark red) of the absolute distance denotes that the vertices exhibit high error. Figure 33 presents the denoising result for the Kinect 2 scanned models. Our approach accomplishes a lower theta mean value yielding equivalent results with other established data-driven approaches [57].

Figure 33 Denoising results and normal angle difference visualization between reconstructed and original Kinect scan with noise level $N \sim (-0.18, 1.4p)$. (a) original mesh (up) and noisy mesh (down), (b) fast and effective, (c) bilateral normal filtering, (d) L0 minimization, (e) guided normal filtering, (f) Cascaded mesh denoising, (g) Feature aware denoising and (h) our approach.

- Impact of patch size, number of clusters and filter parameters:

Figure 34 presents the theta distribution for different settings of selected number of clusters, patch size and bilateral iterations. Purple lines correspond to $N_B = 8$ iterations, blue lines to $N_B = 4$ iterations, green lines to $N_B = 1$ iterations and red lines to $N_B = 0$ iterations (no post processing). As we can observe, 8 iterations significantly improve the result for $N \sim (-0.18, 1.4L_p)$ noise.

Figure 34 Performance evaluation.

Computational complexity evaluation

This subsection presents a comparison of our approach with other methods in terms of computational complexity. To facilitate the performance evaluation we used an open-source implementation in C++ of

state-of-the-art methods [62, 66, 69, 73] available in [74]. To be more specific, the execution was totally performed in C++. For our approach, the autoencoder part of our pipeline is executed in Python TensorFlow, the denoised normal rotation, bilateral normal filtering, and vertex update parts in C++. All the evaluation studies took place in a Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-4790 CPU @ 3.60Hz with 32GB of RAM.

Figure 35 CVAE execution times for 100K faces model and different settings.

Table 25 and Fig. 34 show, our method is much faster than L0 minimization [73] and Guided Normal Filtering (Wangyu Zhang, 2015) and traditional bilateral normal filtering [62]. Compared to fast and effective mesh denoising [66], our method is slower in small models but becomes faster as the number of faces increases. Execution time measurements presented in Table III were computed as the mean value of 10 repetitions. In the case of Rocker Arm counting 18826 faces, our method outperforms all the other approaches. We attribute this observation to the autoencoder complexity. Denoising requires $O(1)$ operations per face removing a large portion of the computational cost.

	Bilateral	Guided	Fast n Effective	L0 min	Feature aware	CVAE 20 pp	CVAE 8 pp
Sculpt (3669V,7342F)	0.1082	0.6465	0.0591	3.5884	0.26743	0.0772	0.0754
Trimmed star (5192V, 10384F)	0.1529	0.9843	0.0869	4.2748	0.41393	0.0995	0.0995
Rocker Arm (9413V,18826F)	0.3242	2.0561	0.1804	11.1609	1.10021	0.1642	0.1617
Chinese Lion (50000 V, 100000F)	2.0508	21.6360	1.5792	110.6100	16.24114	0.9872	0.9624
Gear (250000V,500000F)	8.5630	221.1910	5.7120	2512.2500	180.77456	3.8858	3.7505

Table 25 Execution time, measured in seconds, for presented approaches and noise level $N \sim (0,0.1L_p)$

Impact of parallelization

The input vector contains the normal vector coordinates of n neighbouring faces for a single patch. Each patch is being processed separately through the same processing pipeline. TensorFlow already parallelizes this process and allows to control the number of used CPUs or GPUs. To further elaborate, a noisy model consisting of 100K faces, specifically the "carter" model, was denoised to measure the execution time for the autoencoder part. Six different settings were examined, namely, i) 1 CPU core, ii) 2 CPU cores, iii) 4 CPU cores, iv) 6 CPU cores, v) 8 CPU cores and vi) GPU only. For each different setting, 20 repetitions were performed. Figure 35 presents boxplots summarizing the execution times distribution for each setting.

Defect detection in industrial setting

Saliency maps [75] are essential tools for reliable, accurate and computationally efficient 3D representations, by simplifying the representation of physical. Figure 36 presents visual confirmation, that proper feature preserving denoising can facilitate defect detection in an industrial setting. The first row presents the 3D mesh and the second row, the result of the defect detection process. The color map is related to the Hausdorff distance of each mesh to the ground truth geometry presented in Figure 36. The first column (a,e) presents the original object, the second column (b,f) presents the same object with surface defects that may have originated from the manufacturing process. As Figure 36 reveals, noise prohibits the detection of the defects. The third column (c,g) presents the same 3D mesh with defects and Gaussian noise that may have originated from scanning. Finally, the fourth column presents the denoised object, where the outcome of denoising facilitates accurate detection.

Figure 36 Defect detection with saliency maps. (a,e) Noise-free mesh (b,f) Noise-free mesh mesh with surface defects (c,g) Noisy mesh (d,h) Denoised mesh

5.2 Semantic Layer

In order to use the 3D meshes into several applications like simulations and VR trainings we introduced a semantic layer which describes behavioral information of the components of machines and tools used in A@W. Such information is the **Interaction Type** which describes the kind of interaction with the component (*Pressable, Rotatable, Grabbable, Pullable, Sittable, Wearable*). For some rotational or translational semantics, a handful information is the **Axis** of transformation while a necessary attribute is the **Bounding Box** of the mesh for attaching colliders.

5.2.1 Semantic modelling of workspace tasks and scenarios

Workspace tasks execution and real-world scenarios could be modelled by defining meaningful components and attaching them to the worker or his environment as discussed previously. The core components of the semantic modelling of workspace tasks and scenarios are:

- **Action:** Action is the simplest simulation element. It is linked to an actor (a DHM), a type and an action parameter. Types of actions can be selected from a predefined set or can be customized based on the simulation needs. Predefined actions include walking, sitting, pressing, pulling, pushing and grabbing an object.
- **Action Parameter:** Depending on the type of action, the parameter can correspond to a simple transformation or to a custom composite data structure with multiple objects and constraints. For example, for a “walking” type of action, the action parameter is the destination point while for a “rotate” type of action the parameters are the rotatable object, the rotation angle and the rotation direction.
- **Action Requirement:** An action may meet one or more requirements in order to be successfully completed. The simulation will proceed with the execution of the action only if all defined requirements are fulfilled.
- **Task:** A task is a collection of actions executed in sequential order. It can be performed only once, or it can be repeatable.
- **Process:** A process is a collection of tasks performed in a sequential order.

5.2.2 Authoring tools for work tasks modelling

For the interconnection of the semantic and the geometric layer we designed a 3D Simulator, an authoring tool for the design and simulation of operations of industrial processes. This simulator does not provide an automatic way to model the 3D scene, e.g., using input from depth cameras, but rather provides the authoring tools that allow to add and control properties of the objects, and simulate working tasks and scenarios. For most industrial machines, which are modelled with computer-aided design (CAD) tools, the automatic retrieval of the respective 3D models is easy. However, every-day objects that might be part of a scene and have a vital role in the machinery operation (such as chairs, boxes, natural obstacles) need to be explicitly modelled using 3D modelling software. Of course, if the 3D object details are not crucial for the training simulation, Royalty free objects from popular 3D model databases can be used. For the existing simulation scenarios, Blender 3D creation suite was used.

Many parts of the 3D models and especially those that the worker interacts with, are linked with specific actions. The presented framework provides an improved user interface that facilitates the introduction of a semantic layer into the geometric objects. The main requirement that must be addressed by the designed beforehand, is the segmentation of the whole 3D object into individual parts. The semantics of the 3D objects are labelled according to the Semantic layer of VWM Schema described in Section 5.2. An overall view of the framework user interface is presented in Figure 37.

Figure 37 Overview of the Unity Simulation Framework GUI

The 3D Simulator offers the user the ability to construct training scenarios using graphical interfaces. The components described in Section 0 are initialized or modified through a GUI and through them the user is capable of creating the scenario to be simulated. A real-world scenario can be constructed as a combination of the following components, together with the 3D environment and the Digital Human Model (DHM). The user can create a new task by creating an empty Unity object and adding the “Simple Task” or “Repeatable Task” component script on it. After adding simple/repeatable script, a user interface which can be seen on Figure 39 and Figure 38, will appear. By clicking “Add new Action” a new window will pop up to define the Action, the Action Parameter, and the requirements (if any). An example of action configuration window for a “move” type of action is presented in Figure 40. The Action Parameter for this example is the “Destination” which is a 3D position-transform. In this example the user has not defined any requirements (0-requirements). After pressing the “Add” button, the action is added and displayed into the task component. In a similar manner, a process is a unity game object with the “Process Base” script component attached to it. With the Process Base component interface, the user can add one or more tasks to be executed sequentially. An iteration option is also available where the user can select the iterations number and the DHM will automatically repeat the task(s) for the specified

Figure 38 Simple Task Entry

Figure 39 Repeatable Task Entry

Figure 40 Action Entry Pop-up Window

number of times. After pressing “Add Task” button, a dropdown list with all the available tasks (those who were defined using the Simple/Repeatable Task scripts) will appear.

Figure 41 Process Base User Interface

1.1.1.1 Application Example

In this subsection we will describe and evaluate a real-world training scenario for the 3D Simulator. The training scenario describes the steps required for the operation of an industrial machine. This machine is the drilling machine presented in Section 0. The scenario includes actions for safety assurance for the machine and the worker, as well as operation instructions of drilling a hole in an object of a certain material. It consists of the following 13 specific steps:

Figure 42 The environment of the drilling machine simulation

- 1) Press the emergency button to ensure that the machine is off.
- 2) Open the protection glass.
- 3) Insert the drill bit.
- 4) Close the protection glass.

- 5) Grab the object and insert it under the drill.
- 6) Open the fuse to unlock height adjustment.
- 7) Adjust height with top lever.
- 8) Close the fuse to unlock height adjustment.
- 9) Wear the protection goggles.
- 10) Open the cap of the emergency button.
- 11) Turn the machine on by pressing the green button.
- 12) Drill a hole into the object by pulling the drilling adjustment lever.
- 13) Turn the machine off by pressing the red button.

The proposed scenario requires the 3D modelling and visualization of the drilling machine, the drill bit, the protective glasses, and the bench for the machine. All the models were created using the open-source 3D modelling tool, Blender. The parameterization of the physical object (e.g., bench height) is important for the biophysics assessment module, as it allows to identify the ergonomically best settings for each user.

After importing the models of the Unity 3D scene and based on the components described in the section “Semantic Layer”, the tutorial designer defines the interactable components of the scene and assigns to the DHM the actions. As discussed previously the user must provide for each action the action parameters and requirements (if any) and by combining the actions construct the tasks and processes. For our implementation, we have grouped all those actions into one task entitled “Drill”, so the final process consists only of the “Drill” task, which is a “Simple Task” (non-repeatable). It should be noted that some complex real-world actions may require more than one predefined action in the simulation framework. The records of the 13 steps comprising the drilling operation, along with the 3D models of the working environment, are used to simulate the training scenario and provide visualization of the whole drilling operation and corresponding data for ergonomics assessment. Some of the tutorial steps produced by the simulation module are illustrated in the following figure.

Figure 43 Step 1 (A), Step 8 (B) and Step 12 (C).

5.3 Workplace Semantics

The workplace semantics include those models, model entities and their relationships, which are necessary for the Ageing@Work tools depending on them to function. Such tools are related to the outcomes of tasks T3.3 and T3.5. The fundamental workplace entity is the workstation (or station hereafter), which represents a spatial entity at which work is performed. A station may belong to one of different classes as such each station within a facility is an instance of a different class. Each instance of a station may include one or more machines, tools and materials, needed to carry out its task. Each station instance is also spatially localized within the facility.

Specifically, a station instance entity represents a single instance belonging to a station class. As such, a station class has a one-to-many relationship with one or more station instances. The station class is an intermediary entity type that facilitates representations between task types and station types, therefore allowing the model to be flexible in adding, removing, or modifying said entities. Each station instance, in turn, has a one-to-many relationship with three other entities: Machine, Tool and Material. Machines correspond to the fixed equipment within the factory. Tools correspond to the components used by the machine or worker, necessary to perform a task. Materials refer to consumable entities that are processed or used to facilitate the execution of a task. In order to simplify modelling, it is assumed that each station owns its own set of machines, tools and materials, and those are not shared among stations. Finally, a station is a localized spatial entity, as such it has a one-to-one relationship with a location that corresponds to its placement within the facility.

Station classes are related in a many-to-many relationship to task templates, in such a way that dictates that instance of a task template can be executed in one or more station classes. As an example, a task that regards CNC machining can be performed at a CNC Station, and will require the right machine (CNC machine) tools (cutting tools, mounting tools) and materials (cutting stock, wasteboards etc). Because of this relationship, stations are considered resources that play an important role in shift scheduling (T3.5).

The workplace semantics outlined herein are modelled considering also the semantic layer of section 5.2 outlined previously. In a sense, the workplace semantics complete the integration between the semantic layer, which focuses on the specific tasks at hand, the topological organization at the facility level, and the shift and task orchestration at the facility level. As such, the workplace semantics do not deal with the level of detail that the semantic layer does, but they include higher-level information that pertains to the whole workplace, and its connection with job orchestration.

Figure 44 Relationships between A@W model entity groups

As an example, consider a facility that performs material processing. The facility may comprise several different station classes, depending on the type of work that each station specializes. One station class may be a CNC mill, another one a drilling station, a CNC brake and so on. More than one instance of each station may be present in the facility, each in a separate location. In accordance, there might be several task types, or templates, that a station class is suitable for performing. For instance, cutting sheet metal is one type of task that can be performed at the brake, and similarly CNC machining can be performed at the mill. Throughout one shift, there might be several instances of machining or cutting tasks that need to be performed. Combining the above with specific skills that are required for each task type, the possession of skills by workers and availability of workers per shift also completes the integration with the job orchestration part.

Figure 45 High level UML semantic overview of the workplace and scheduling entities and relationships

In section 5.2.1 the core components of modeling have been introduced as Process, Task and Action, where Process represents the highest hierarchical level, while Action represents the lowest, and Task is in between. Workplace semantics mainly refer to the Task level, as it is the unit that corresponds to a single unit of work that can be performed at a station instance at any time. In turn, the task represents the entity associated with worker skills, which facilitates shift scheduling depending on the process requirements set by the manager.

6. Conclusion

In this deliverable we presented the user modelling and workplace modelling approaches in Ageing@Work. The first part of the deliverable showed the worker’s virtual user model and its capabilities to persist information in different dimensions such as demographic, lifestyle, workability, health and behavioural information. Specific data schemas were also presented to facilitate the understanding of the model. Furthermore, the computational part of the wVUM was presented, according to the rule-based

logic of our system and its predictive potential, towards improving the self-management of worker's health behaviours. The wVUM communication capabilities through the REST architecture to promote the extensibility and scalability of our solution were also presented.

The second part of the deliverable was devoted to the presentation of methods and results for all the steps of the workplace simulation pipeline, from the creation of 3D models – based on mesh or point cloud acquisition, denoising and outliers removal, or through computer-aided design – to their use within the simulation of complex working tasks in multiple levels, i.e. for each individual worker or for work orchestration. A variety of quantitative and visual results was obtained for the evaluation of the developed methods and tools. The implemented simulation framework was utilized for the needs of the Ageing@Work pilot cases, nevertheless it should be mentioned that it allows the creation of a large variety of different objects/machines, as well as the simulation of multiple different actions performed by a digital human model (acting as a digital twin of the worker). The outcomes of this deliverable have already been exploited in the other connected tasks of Ageing@Work.

7. References

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8 . ANNEX I

PARTICIPANT GENERAL INFORMATION

This section will be filled by the assigned researcher.

DATE: _____

PARTICIPANT ID: _____

(Be sure you include the unique ID assigned to each of the participant at the beginning of the project)

Evaluation period: Baseline

Intermediate (3 months)

Final (6 months)

Instructions

This is the complete version of the questionnaires for the Ageing@Work system evaluation. The evaluation process is comprised by 3 periods plus a initial questionnaire to build the personal Worker Virtual Model.

Following table presents the periods each of the questionnaires should be administered.

Construct	Questionnaire	S	T0	T1	T2
Health and working conditions questionnaire	Socio-demographic data and virtual coach data	X			
Quality of life	SF-12		X	X	X
Work related well-being and psychosocial conditions at work	COPSOQ		X	X	X
Technology acceptance	UTAUT			X	X

Health and working conditions questionnaire

Instructions

Administration information. This questionnaire is a self-administrated questionnaire that should be administrated at in the recruitment process if the participant fills the inclusion criteria. The objective of the project is to provide the basic information required to contextualize the participant and create his/her personal virtual model.

Health and working conditions questionnaire

Dear Participant!

The survey is conducted within the Ageing@Work Project that your company is involved in.

This questionnaire is aimed at assessment of working conditions and their relationship to employees' health. It consists of two main parts: your health status and working conditions. [The survey is anonymous.](#)

The individual data will not be available to any of your supervisors. We encourage you to give your honest opinion!

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA
1. Where do you live? _____ Floor: _____
2. Where do you work? _____ Address : _____ Floor: _____
3. Gender: ₁ <input type="checkbox"/> Male ₂ <input type="checkbox"/> Female
4. Are you: ₁ <input type="checkbox"/> Single ₂ <input type="checkbox"/> In relationship or Married ₃ <input type="checkbox"/> Divorced / Separated ₄ <input type="checkbox"/> Widowed
5. How long have you been involved in the present work tasks? _____
6. What is the title of your main paid job/occupation? _____
7. A household may have different sources of income and more than one household member may contribute to it. Thinking of your household's total monthly income, is your household able to make ends meet...? ₁ <input type="checkbox"/> Very easily ₂ <input type="checkbox"/> Easily ₃ <input type="checkbox"/> Fairly easily ₄ <input type="checkbox"/> With some difficulty ₅ <input type="checkbox"/> With difficulty ₆ <input type="checkbox"/> With great difficulty
8. Are you, in your household, the person who contributes the most to the household income? ₁ <input type="checkbox"/> Yes ₂ <input type="checkbox"/> No ₃ <input type="checkbox"/> All equally
9. In general, how often are you involved in any of the following activities outside work? a. Caring for and/or educating your children, grandchildren ₁ <input type="checkbox"/> Daily ₂ <input type="checkbox"/> Several times a week ₃ <input type="checkbox"/> Several times a month ₄ <input type="checkbox"/> Less often ₅ <input type="checkbox"/> Never ₆ <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable b. Caring for elderly/disabled relatives ₁ <input type="checkbox"/> Daily ₂ <input type="checkbox"/> Several times a week ₃ <input type="checkbox"/> Several times a month ₄ <input type="checkbox"/> Less often ₅ <input type="checkbox"/> Never ₆ <input type="checkbox"/> Not applicable

HEALTH AND CAPABILITIES

1. Assume that your work ability at its best have a value of 10 points. How many points would you give your **current work ability**? (0 means that you currently cannot work at all)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Cannot work									Best ever

2. Assume that your job performance at its best has a value of 10 points. How many points would you give your **current job performance**?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Very poor									Excellent

3. **How much do you move and exert yourself physically during your leisure time?**

If your activity varies greatly between, for example, summer and winter, try to estimate an average. The question refers to the past year.

Mark only one option!

Physically inactive

Almost completely inactive, reading, watching television, watching movies, using computers or doing other sedentary activities, during leisure time 1

Some light physical activity

Physically active for at least 4 hours/week, such as riding a bicycle or walking to work, walking with the family, gardening, fishing, table tennis, bowling etc. 2

Regular physical activity and training

Spending time doing heavy gardening, running, swimming, playing tennis, badminton, calisthenics and similar activities, for at least 2-3 hours/week. 3

Regular hard physical training for competitive sports

Spending time running, orienteering, skiing, swimming, playing football, handball etc. several times per week 4

4. How do you spend your leisure time apart from physical activity? Add a number from 1 (favourite activity) to 5 (least favourite activity)

___ Restaurant/Pub/Cafeteria/Bar Which one ? _____

___ Museum/monument/cinema/theatre/exhibition Which one ? _____

___ Shop Which one ? _____

___ Gym/stadium/court/sports centre/park Which one ? _____

___ Meeting with friends or relatives at a home (home leisure activities) Which one ? _____

<p>5. How often do you go to a Restaurant/Pub/Cafeteria/Bar?</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 2</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 3</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 4</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 5</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 6</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 7</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 8</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 9</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday	
<p>6. How often do you go to museum/monument/cinema/theatre/exhibition?</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 2</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 3</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 4</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 5</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 6</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 7</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 8</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 9</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday	
<p>7. How often do you shop?</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 2</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 3</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 4</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 5</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 6</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 7</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 8</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 9</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday	
<p>8. How often do you go to gym/stadium/court/sports centre/park?</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse; text-align: center;"> <tr> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 2</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 3</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 4</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 5</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 6</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 7</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 8</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 9</td> <td style="width: 10%;"><input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday</td> </tr> </table>	<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 Never	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 6	<input type="checkbox"/> 7	<input type="checkbox"/> 8	<input type="checkbox"/> 9	<input type="checkbox"/> 10 Everyday	
<p>9. Do you smoke / use tobacco? <input type="checkbox"/> YES <input type="checkbox"/> NO</p>										
<p>10. How many portions of fruits and vegetables do you eat per day? (A portion of fruit or vegetables is 80g. eg. 1 medium sized piece of fruit; 1 dessert bowl of salad; a large handful of berries or grapes; 2 broccoli spears; 3 heaped tablespoons of peas, carrots or sweetcorn)</p> <p>_____ portions / day</p>										
<p>11. How many alcoholic drinks do you usually have each week? _____</p> <p>(Standard drink: Beer: 1 can (373ml); Wine: 1 medium glass (125ml) Port or sherry: 1 small glass (60ml) Spirits/liqueur: 1 nip (30ml)</p>										
<p>12. What is an average amount of water you drink per day?</p> <p>_____ liter(s)</p>										
<p>13. In general, I would say my health is:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5 Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> 4 Very good <input type="checkbox"/> 3 Good <input type="checkbox"/> 2 Fair <input type="checkbox"/> 1 Poor</p>										
<p>14. I have problems with vision: <input type="checkbox"/> 1 YES (check below) <input type="checkbox"/> 2 NO</p> <p>If YES: <input type="checkbox"/> 1 Near <input type="checkbox"/> 2 Far <input type="checkbox"/> 3 I am colorblind <input type="checkbox"/> 4 Other (please describe)</p>										
<p>15. If an answer to the question 10 is yes, my vision with correction glasses/lenses is:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> 2 Good <input type="checkbox"/> 3 Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> 4 Poor</p>										
<p>16. I have problem with hearing: <input type="checkbox"/> 1 YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2 NO</p>										
<p>17. I have a history of seizures: <input type="checkbox"/> 1 YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2 NO</p>										
<p>18. I have problem with lifting my arms: <input type="checkbox"/> 1 YES <input type="checkbox"/> 2 NO</p>										

How easily do you get dizzy or lose concentration?

19.

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Not at all									Extremely

20. If an answer to the question 12 is YES, my hearing with hearing aid is:

1 Excellent 2 Good 3 Moderate 4 Poor

21. In your opinion, are you able to:

a. Run a half kilometre? 1 Without difficulty 2 With difficulty or unable

b. Walk two kilometres? 1 Without difficulty 2 With difficulty or unable

c. Climb several flight or stairs? 1 Without difficulty 2 With difficulty or unable

22. In the past 12 months, how many days in total were you absent from work for reasons of health problems?

_____ days

23. Do you have any illness or health problem which has lasted, or is expected to last, for more than 6 months?

1 YES 2 NO

24. Over the last 12 months, did you have any of the following health problems?

a. backache 1 YES 2 NO

b. muscular pains in shoulders, neck and/or upper limbs 1 YES 2 NO

c. muscular pains in lower limbs (hips, legs, knees, feet etc.) 1 YES 2 NO

d. overall fatigue 1 YES 2 NO

e. other (describe)

25. Physical fatigue involves extreme physical tiredness and an inability to engage in physical activity. During the PAST 12 MONTHS, how often did you feel physically exhausted at the end of the workday?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Never									Everyday

26. Over the last 6 months, did you experienced overall fatigue?

1 YES 2 NO

27. How often do you have negative feelings such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, depression?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Never									Everyday

28. How well are you able to concentrate?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Not at all									Extremely

29. How well are you able to handle multiple things at the same time?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Not at all									Extremely

30. How satisfied are you with your sleep?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Very dissatisfied									Very satisfied

31. **Stress** means the situation when a person feels tense, restless, nervous, or anxious, or is unable to sleep at night because his mind is troubled all the time.
How often have you been stressed during the last 4 weeks?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Never									Everyday

32. I am confident in my ability to solve problems that I might face in life
(For example: I can usually handle whatever comes my way, If I try hard enough I can overcome difficult problems, I can stick to my aims and accomplish my goals)

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Strongly disagree									Strongly agree

33. How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Very dissatisfied									Very satisfied

34. How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Very dissatisfied									Very satisfied

35. How often do you socialize with friends / neighbours / relatives?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Never									Everyday

36. How would you rate your quality of life?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Very poor									Very good

37. Do you use any mobile app (FitBit etc) to measure your daily activities?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>
Yes	No

If yes, which one ones?

WELLBEING AT WORK

1. Do you feel motivated and involved in your work?

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Not at all									Extremely

2. Regarding your work in general. How pleased are you with your job as a whole, everything taken into consideration?

3.

1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
Very dissatisfied									Very satisfied

4. Do you feel that your work drains so much of your energy that it has a negative effect on your private life?
 1 To a very large extent 2 To a large extent 3 Somewhat
 4 To a small extent 5 To a very small extent

5. How often can you take a break?
 Every half an hour Every hour Every 2-4 hours
 Once during a workday Never

6. How long do your breaks last?

7. Do you feel that your work takes so much of your time that it has a negative effect on your private life?
 1 To a very large extent 2 To a large extent 3 Somewhat
 4 To a small extent 5 To a very small extent

8. Are you worried about becoming unemployed?
 1 To a very large extent 2 To a large extent 3 Somewhat
 4 To a small extent 5 To a very small extent

9. Are you worried about it being difficult for you to find another job if you became unemployed?
 1 To a very large extent 2 To a large extent 3 Somewhat
 4 To a small extent 5 To a very small extent

10. In a scale of 1 to 10, meaning 1 very dissatisfied and 10 very satisfied, how would you rate your income?

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	----

Mean time to complete task

1) What is your best turnaround time?

2) What is your most likely turnaround time?

3) What is your worst turnaround time?

JOB DEMANDS

1. How physically exerting do you perceive your current work?

1 No exertion	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10 Maximum exertion
------------------	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---	------------------------

Please indicate, using the following scale, are you exposed at work to ...?										
2. Carrying or moving heavy loads										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
3. Tiring or painful positions (e.g. working with hand lifted, squatting, kneeling)										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
4. Standing										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
5. Sitting										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
6. Repetitive hand or arm movements										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
7. Vibrations from hand tools, machinery, etc.										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
8. High temperatures which make you perspire even when not working										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
9. Low temperatures whether indoors or outdoors										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
10. From a scale of 1 to 10, how much humidity does the environment of your work have?										
11.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>	8 <input type="checkbox"/>	9 <input type="checkbox"/>	10 <input type="checkbox"/>
	Not at all									Extremely
11. Breathing in smoke, fumes (such as welding or exhaust fumes), powder or dust (such as mineral dust) etc.										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
12. Handling or being in skin contact with chemical products or substances										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
13. Breathing in vapours such as solvents and thinners										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
14. Does your main paid job involve working with computers, laptops, smartphones etc.?										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost all of the time 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¾ of the time 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Around half of the time 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Around ¼ of the time 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Almost never 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Never										
15. How often do you not have time to complete all your work tasks?										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever										
16. Do you get behind with your work?										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever										
17. Do you work at a high pace throughout the day?										
1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever										

18. Do you have to work very fast? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
19. Is your work varied? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
20. Do you have to do the same thing over and over again? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
21. Do you feel isolated from colleagues while working? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
22. Do you have to keep your eyes on lots of things while you work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
23. Does your work require that you remember a lot of things? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
24. Does your work demand that you are good at coming up with new ideas? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
25. Does your work require you to make difficult decisions? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
26. a. How often do you get help and support from your immediate superior, if needed? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
27. How often do you get help and support from your colleagues, if needed? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
28. Have you been involved in quarrels or conflicts at your workplace during the last 12 months? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
29. Do you have a large degree of influence on the decisions concerning your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
30. Do you have the possibility of learning new things through your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
31. Can you use your skills or expertise in your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
32. Is there space for elderly employees in your company? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
33. Are you working as an employee or are you self-employed? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Employee 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Self-employed
34. What kind of employment contract do you have in your main job? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Contract of unlimited duration 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Contract of limited duration 3 <input type="checkbox"/> A temporary employment agency contract 4 <input type="checkbox"/> An apprenticeship or other training scheme 5 <input type="checkbox"/> No contract 6 <input type="checkbox"/> Other (describe): _____
35. How many hours do you usually work per week in your main paid job? _____
36. During last 12 months, have you worked in more than one location? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> YES 2 <input type="checkbox"/> NO
37. Do you always use personal protective equipment when it is required? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> YES 2 <input type="checkbox"/> NO
38. Do you trust in emergency/rescue procedures and staff in your company? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> YES 2 <input type="checkbox"/> NO

39. Regarding the health and safety risks related to performance of your job, how well informed would you say you are? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very well informed 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Well informed 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Not very well informed 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all well informed
40. How satisfied are you with your access to health services? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very unsatisfied 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Neither satisfied not unsatisfied 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied
41. Does your employer provide you an additional (private) health insurance? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> YES 2 <input type="checkbox"/> NO 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
42. Do you have to take stairs at your workplace? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent

Personality Traits – Big Five You find yourself as a person that...	
1.	Tends to be quiet. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
2.	Is compassionate, has a soft heart. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
3.	Tends to be disorganized. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
4.	Worries a lot. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
5.	Is fascinated by art, music or literature. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
6.	Is dominant, acts as a leader. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
7.	Is sometimes rude to others. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
8.	Has difficulty getting started on tasks. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
9.	Tends to feel depressed, blue. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
10.	Has little interest in abstract ideas. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
11.	Is full of energy 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever

12. Assumes the best about people. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
13. Is a reliable, can always be counted on. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
14. Is emotionally stable, not easily upset. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
15. Is original, comes up with new ideas. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
16. Is outgoing, sociable. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
17. Can be cold and uncaring. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
18. Keeps things neat and tidy. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
19. Is relaxed, handles stress well. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
20. Has few artistic interests. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
21. Prefers to have others take charge. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
22. Is respectful, treats others with respect. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
23. Is persistent, works until the task is finished. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
24. Feels secure, comfortable with self. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
25. Is complex, a deep thinker. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
26. Is less active than other people. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
27. Tends to find fault with others. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
28. Can be somewhat careless. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever

29. Is temperamental, gets emotionally easily. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
30. Has little creativity. 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever

Professional Skills
1) Do you have any driving license <input type="checkbox"/> Truck <input type="checkbox"/> JCB <input type="checkbox"/> Bus <input type="checkbox"/> Car <input type="checkbox"/> Motorcycle <input type="checkbox"/> Other
2) How often do you manage your time successfully ? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
3) How good are your leadership skills? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very Poor 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Poor 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Good 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent
4) How good are your skills in public speaking? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very Poor 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Poor 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Good 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent
5) How would you characterize your flexibility in operations and thinking? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very Poor 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Poor 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Good 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent
6) How would you rate your ability to work in teams? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Very Poor 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Poor 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Intermediate 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Good 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent

PHQ 9
Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following problems?
1) Little interest or pleasure in doing things. <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day
2) Feeling down depressed or hopeless. <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day
3) Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much. <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day
4) Feeling tired or having little energy <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day
5) Poor appetite or overeating <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day
6) Feeling bad about yourself, or that you are a failure or have let yourself down or your family down <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day
7) Trouble concentrating on things, such as reading the newspaper or watching television

<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day
8) Moving or speaking so slowly that other people could have noticed. Or the opposite, being so figety or restless that you have been moving around a lot more than usual. <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day
9) Thoughts that you would be better off dead, or of hurting yourself. <input type="checkbox"/> Not at all <input type="checkbox"/> Several days <input type="checkbox"/> More than half the days <input type="checkbox"/> Nearly every day

Goal

1) What would you like to improve at your workplace and home life? (max 100 words)

Day Routine

1) Please provide us with a short description of your day routine (max 100 words)

SF12 HEALTH SURVEY

This survey asks for your views about your health. This information will help keep track of how you feel and how well you are able to do your usual activities. Answer each question by choosing just one answer. If you are unsure how to answer a question, please give the best answer you can.

<p>1. In general, would you say your health is</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Very Good 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Good 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Fair 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Poor</p>						
<p>The following two questions are about activities you might do during a typical day. Does YOUR HEALTH NOW LIMIT YOU in these activities? If so, how much?</p>						
	Yes, Limited A Lot	Yes, Limited A Little	No, Limited At All			
2. MODERATE ACTIVITIES, such as moving a table, pushing a vacuum cleaner, bowling, or playing golf:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>			
3. Climbing SEVERAL flights of stairs:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>			
<p>During the PAST 4 WEEKS have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular activities AS A RESULT OF YOUR PHYSICAL HEALTH?</p>						
	Yes	No				
4. ACCOMPLISHED LESS than you would like:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>				
5. Were limited in the KIND of work or other activities:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>				
<p>During the PAST 4 WEEKS, were you limited in the kind of work you do or other regular activities AS A RESULT OF ANY EMOTIONAL PROBLEMS (such as feeling depressed or anxious)?</p>						
	Yes	No				
6. ACCOMPLISHED LESS than you would like:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>				
7. Didn't do work or other activities as CAREFULLY as usual:	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>				
<p>8. During the PAST 4 WEEKS, how much did PAIN interfere with your normal work (including both work outside the home and housework)?</p> <p>1 <input type="checkbox"/> Not At All 2 <input type="checkbox"/> A Little Bit 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Moderately 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Quite a Bit 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Extremely</p>						
<p>The next three questions are about how you feel and how things have been DURING THE PAST 4 WEEKS. For each question, please give the one answer that comes closest to the way you have been feeling. How much of the time during the PAST 4 WEEKS –</p>						
	All of the Time	Most of the Time	A Good Bit of the Time	Some of the Time	A Little of the Time	None of the Time
9. Have you felt calm and peaceful?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>
10. Did you have a lot of energy?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>
11. Have you felt downhearted and blue?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>
12. During the PAST 4 WEEKS, how much of the time has your PHYSICAL HEALTH OR EMOTIONAL PROBLEMS interfered with your social activities (like visiting with friends, relatives, etc.)?	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>

COPSOQ (short version) Work related well-being

This survey asks for your views about your psychosocial conditions and health promotion in your work. This information will help keep track of how you feel in your work and collect important information to prompt preventive actions. Answer each question by choosing just one answer. If you are unsure how to answer a question, please give the best answer you can.

Quantitative Demands
1. Do you have to work very fast? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never/hardly ever
2. Is your workload unevenly distributed so it piles up? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never/hardly ever
3. How often do you have time to complete all your tasks? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never/hardly ever
Emotional Demands
4. Does your work put you in emotionally disturbing situations? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
5. Do you get emotionally involved in your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
Demands for Hiding Emotions
6. Does your work require that you hide your feelings? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
Influence at Work
7. Do you have a large degree of influence concerning your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
8. Can you influence the amount of work assigned to you? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
9. Do you have any influence on what you do at work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
Possibilities for Development
10. Does your work require you to take the initiative? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
11. Do you have the possibility of learning new things through your work? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
Degree of Freedom at Work
12. Can you decide when to take a break? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 5 <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever
Meaning of Work
13. Is your work meaningful? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
14. Do you feel that the work you do is important? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent
Commitment to the Workplace
15. Would you like to stay at your current place of work for the rest of your working life? 1 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent 2 <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat 4 <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent 5 <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent

<p>16. Do you feel that your place of work is of great personal importance to you? <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
Predictability
<p>17. At your place of work, are you informed well in advance concerning for example important decisions, changes, or plans for the future? <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
<p>18. Do you receive all the information you need in order to your work well? <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
Quality of Leadership
<p>19. To what extent would you say that your immediate superior ...</p> <p>a. Is good at work planning? <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p> <p>b. Is good at solving conflicts? <input type="checkbox"/> To a very large extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a large extent <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> To a small extent <input type="checkbox"/> To a very small extent</p>
Social Support
<p>20. How often do you get help and support from your colleagues? <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever</p>
<p>21. How often do you get help and support from your immediate superior? <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever</p>
Feedback at Work
<p>22. How often does your superior talk with you about how well you carry out your work? <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever</p>
<p>23. How often do your colleagues talk with you about how well you carry out your work? <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever</p>
Sense of Community
<p>24. Is there good co-operation between you and your colleagues? <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly ever</p>
<p>25. Do you feel part of a community at your place of work? <input type="checkbox"/> Always <input type="checkbox"/> Often <input type="checkbox"/> Sometimes <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom <input type="checkbox"/> Never / hardly eve</p>
Insecurity at Work
<p>26. Are you worried about...</p> <p>a. Becoming unemployed? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>b. New technology making you redundant? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>c. It being difficult for you to find another job if you become unemployed? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>d. Being transferred to another job against your will? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
Job Satisfaction
<p>27. Regarding your work in general. How pleased are you with...</p> <p>a. Your work prospects? <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Highly unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant</p> <p>b. The physical working conditions? <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Highly unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant</p> <p>c. The way your abilities are used?</p>

<p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Highly unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant </p> <p>d. Your job as a whole, everything taken into consideration?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Very satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Satisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Highly unsatisfied <input type="checkbox"/> Not relevant </p>
General Health
<p>28. In general, would you say your health is</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> Excellent <input type="checkbox"/> Very Good <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Poor </p>
Mental Health
<p>29. These questions are about how you feel and how things have been with you during the past 4 weeks. For each question, please give the one answer that comes closest to the way you have been feeling. How much of the time during the past 4 weeks ¹–</p> <p>a. Have you ever been a very nervous person?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> A little of the time <input type="checkbox"/> None of the time </p> <p>b. Have you felt so down in the dumps that nothing could cheer you up?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> A little of the time <input type="checkbox"/> None of the time </p> <p>c. Have you been a happy person?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> A little of the time <input type="checkbox"/> None of the time </p>
Vitality²
<p>30. These questions are about how you feel and how things have been with you during the past 4 weeks. For each question, please give the one answer that comes closest to the way you have been feeling. How much of the time during the past 4 weeks –</p> <p>a. Did you feel full of pep?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> A little of the time <input type="checkbox"/> None of the time </p> <p>b. Did you feel worn out?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> A little of the time <input type="checkbox"/> None of the time </p> <p>c. Did you feel tired?</p> <p style="text-align: center;"> <input type="checkbox"/> All of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Most of the time <input type="checkbox"/> Some of the time <input type="checkbox"/> A little of the time <input type="checkbox"/> None of the time </p>

UTAUT Acceptability of the solution

This survey asks for your views about the technology you have used. This information will help keep track your intention to use the technology and possible acceptance barriers. Answer each

¹ This domain also includes Have you felt calm and peaceful? And Have you felt downhearted and blue? The questions are also in SF-12 and should be added in this section to complete the evaluation

² This domain also includes the question Did you have a lot of energy? That is in the SF-12 to evaluate add the appropriate answer her

question by choosing just one answer. If you are unsure how to answer a question, please give the best answer you can.

Effort Expectancy							
	Fully disagree	Disagree	Some-what disagree	Nor agree, nor Disagree	Some What agree	Agree	Fully agree
EE1: My interaction with the system is clear and understandable	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
EE2: It is easy for me to become skilful at using the system	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
I find the system easy to use	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
Learning to operate the system is easy to me	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
Performance expectancy							
	Fully disagree	Disagree	Some-what disagree	Nor agree, nor Disagree	Some What agree	Agree	Fully agree
PE1: I find the system useful for my purposes (daily living/job)	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
PE2: Using the system enables me to accomplish task more quickly.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
PE3: Using the system increases my productivity	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
PE4: If I use the system, I will increase my changes of getting better quality of life	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
Social influence							
	Fully disagree	Disagree	Some-what disagree	Nor agree, nor Disagree	Some What agree	Agree	Fully agree
SI1: People who influence my behaviour think that I should use the system	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
SI2: People who are important to me think that I should use the system.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
SI3: Management would motivate to use of the system	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
Facilitating conditions							
	Fully disagree	Disagree	Some-what disagree	Nor agree, nor Disagree	Some What agree	Agree	Fully agree
FC1: I have the resources necessary to use the IoT device	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
FC2: I have the knowledge necessary to use the system.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
FC3: The system is not compatible with other systems I use during my working hours	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>
FC4: A specific person (or group) is available for assistance with the system difficulties.	1 <input type="checkbox"/>	2 <input type="checkbox"/>	3 <input type="checkbox"/>	4 <input type="checkbox"/>	5 <input type="checkbox"/>	6 <input type="checkbox"/>	7 <input type="checkbox"/>

